

Training material on the production of healthy, high-quality organic seed

Authors: Stephanie Klaedtke (ITAB), Stéphanie Mothes (ITAB), Maike Bender (Dottenfelderhof), Valentin Gfeller (FiBL-CH), Diego Guidotti (Aedit SRL), Steven Groot (WUR & International Seed Academy), Kis Gyöngyi Györéné (ÖMKi), , Jan Kodde (WUR), Mária Megyeri (OMKI), Monika Messmer (FiBL-CH), Baćanović-Šišić (Bingenheimer Saatgut AG), Gaspard de Tournemire (ITAB), Carl Vollenweider (Dottenfelderhof), Mariano Iossa (FiBL-Europe)

Deliverable Number	D3.2
Work Package	WP3
Deliverable type	DEC
Dissemination level	Public
Deliverable Lead partner	ITAB
Due date	30 September 2025
Submission date	28 October 2025
Version	V2
Reviewers	Mariano Iossa
Contact	Stephanie.klaedtke@itab.asso.fr

Funded by the European Union (grant no. 101059872), the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (Contract no. 22.0412) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA, nor SERI or UKRI.

UK Research
and Innovation

History of changes

Version	Date	Author	Comments
V1	17/10/2025	Stephanie Mothes & Stephanie Klaedtke	Deliverable writing and revision
V2	21/10/2025	Mariano Iossa	Final quality check and reporting

LiveSeeding - Organic seed and plant breeding to accelerate sustainable and diverse food systems in Europe is a 4-year Innovation Action funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The project started in October 2022 and brings together 37 organisations operating in 16 European countries. LiveSeeding provides science-based evidence and best practice solutions to help achieve 100 % organic seed.

LiveSeeding contributes to the transition towards environmentally-friendly, climate-neutral, healthy and fair food systems through a **PUSH-PULL-ENABLE strategy** to

- enhance the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PUSH),
- increase and stabilise the market demand for organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PULL),
- foster an enabling policy and regulatory environment where both demand and supply can harmoniously and productively negotiate without irrelevant constraints due to legal restrictions and/or regulatory fragmentation (ENABLE).

LiveSeeding addresses the topics in a **holistic multi-actor, multi-stakeholder, participatory approach** involving stakeholders along the value chain in 17 local **Living Labs (LLs)** and 3 established networks of organic breeders (**ECO-PB**), seed savers (**ECLLD**) and Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (**MUFPP**). 15 European countries cover the different pedoclimatic zones and socio-economic contexts, including countries with a low level of development in organic seed and breeding in East and South Europe.

Table of Contents

SUMMARY.....	4
1. LEARNING NEEDS ASSESSMENT	7
1.1 GENERAL OBJECTIVES	7
1.2 UNDERSTANDING THE TARGET AUDIENCE	8
1.3 CARRYING OUT A TASK ANALYSIS.....	11
1.3.1 General approach.....	11
1.3.2 Results of the task analysis	14
2. MAPPING AND ANALYSIS OF THE EXISTING TRAINING OFFER	17
2.1 GENERAL APPROACH	17
2.2 RESULTS.....	18
2.2.1 Existing training courses.....	18
2.2.2 Conclusion on the offer of existing training courses	20
2.2.3 Learning resources available on knowledge portals and other websites	20
3. OFFERING METHODOLOGICAL SUPPORT TO TRAINING DESIGNERS	22
3.1 TRAINING ENGINEERING	22
3.2 TRAINERS' TRAINING ON SEED HARVEST, DRYING AND STORAGE FOR ORGANIC SEED PRODUCTION.....	23
4. DEVELOPMENT OF THE LIVESEEDING TRAINING MATERIAL	25
4.1 THE CHOICE OF SELF-PACED LEARNING.....	25
4.1.1 Definition	25
4.1.2 Why self-paced learning?	26
4.2 BASIC PEDAGOGICAL STRUCTURE OF OUR E-LEARNING COURSES	27
4.3 HOSTING THE E-MODULES AND PROVIDING A USER INTERFACE	29
5. PRESENTATION OF THE E-LEARNING SPACE AND ASSOCIATED RESOURCES	29
5.1 INTRODUCTION & LINK TO THE TASK REFERENCE FRAMEWORK	29
5.2 PRESENTATION OF LEARNING PATHS AND E-LEARNING MODULES.....	30
5.2.1 Learning paths	30
5.2.2 The modules	33
5.3 APPROPRIATION OF RESOURCES AND FRAMING OF RULES OF USE: CHOICE OF CC LICENCE	34
BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	35
ANNEXES.....	2
ANNEX 1: MIND MAP OF KEY TASKS FOR THE PRODUCTION OF HIGH-QUALITY, HEALTHY ORGANIC SEED	2

ANNEX 2: TASK REFERENCE FRAMEWORK WITH PRIORITY VOTE	2
ANNEX 3: LIST AND DESCRIPTION OF EXISTING TRAINING COURSES, OUTCOME OF THE BENCHMARKING PROCESS	8
ANNEX 4: LIBRARY OF LEARNING RESOURCES - OUTCOME OF THE BENCHMARKING PROCESS...	14
ANNEX 5: TOOLS DESIGNED FOR TASK 3.5.....	22
ANNEX 6: PROGRAMME OF THE TRAINERS' TRAINING IN WAGENINGEN 4-5 APRIL 2023 : SEED MATURITY, DRYING & STORAGE.....	32

Summary

The use of organic seeds is one of the pillars of organic agriculture. This requirement was stated in the first European regulation on Organic farming (EEC No 2092/91) and reinforced in subsequent regulations (EC No 834/2007). However, the supply of organic seeds remains largely insufficient in terms of quantity, quality and diversity, leaving the sector dependent on the use of 'untreated' seeds from conventional propagation through the use of derogation. Deliverable D3.2 identifies key skills for the production of high quality organic seed, and provides exhaustive compilation of training materials in organic seed production based on a training needs assessment.

Seeds are currently one of the strategic domains for the future of organic farming, facing a double challenge:

- the European 'Farm2Fork' strategy, which aims to achieve 25% of certified organic agricultural land by 2030, i.e. more than double the current area.
- the new European Organic Regulation (EU) 848/2018, which aims to phase out derogations for the use of untreated conventional seeds and achieve 100% certified organic seeds by 2035.

This dual challenge requires a strong increase in organic seed production: an ambitious goal that highlights the need for qualified seed producers to increase the quantities of organic seed of many crop species, but also to ensure seed quality. Organic farming needs access to high-quality organic seeds representing a wide and varied range of varieties suited to a diversity of environments and uses.

In the absence or stringent limitation of synthetic inputs, organic farming favours preventive methods for disease and pest control. Having healthy, vigorous seeds is one of the cornerstones of this prophylactic approach. Scientific studies and practical experience show that vigorous seeds and young seedlings are more resistant to abiotic stresses (e.g. crusted soil or water stress) and biotic stresses (e.g. weeds and diseases, particularly soil-borne diseases). Ensuring seedling vigour through good physiological seed quality therefore contributes to crop health and performance. In addition, controlling seed-borne diseases requires monitoring and appropriate measures. In organic seed production, attention is focused not only on the health status of seeds and processes for curative sanitation, but also on all interactions between plants, soil and practices during seed multiplication and germination.

The LiveSeeding project aims at enhancing the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming. **Training in organic seed production** key concepts, practices, strategies and tools available **represents a key approach to involve new actors and changing practices of established ones to improve both the availability and the quality of organic seed** .

Deliverable 3.2 describes the process by which key skills for the production of high quality organic seed were listed, available training resources were collected and priority training needs identified. It also consists of an exhaustive compilation of **training materials in organic seed production**.

The deliverable is structured in five chapters. **Chapter 1** analyses learning needs, defining training objectives and target audiences while identifying key skills and tasks in organic seed production. **Chapter 2** reviews existing training offers and resources, highlighting gaps in organic seed quality management that the project addresses. **Chapter 3** presents methodological support provided to partners, including training design tools and a trainers' course on seed harvest, drying and storage. **Chapter 4** describes the development of the LiveSeeding e-learning material, explaining the choice of self-paced learning and the structure of the online modules. **Chapter 5** introduces the e-learning space, its learning paths and modules, and the open Creative Commons licensing that allows their broad use and adaptation.

Training materials are divided into eight thematic modules, structured in 3-7 units each, covering general principles of seed health and quality in organic production, up to more specific aspects, such as the propagation of organic heterogeneous material or requirements when propagating or cultivating common bunt resistant wheat varieties. Modules are:

Module 11: General introduction to organic seed quality & health
Module 12: Seed maturity and harvest
Module 13: Seed drying and storage
Module 14: An introduction to seed microbiota
Module 15: Hot water treatments for the sanitation of vegetable seeds
Module 16: OHM, General introduction, seed production and traceability
Module 17: Tracking OHM, a digital tool for the notification, traceability of OHM seed
Module 18: Growing and propagating bunt resistant wheat varieties

Links to modules and learning materials repositories are available in **section 5.2.2** .

The modules numbering is a continuum from other modules developed under other Work Packages. Together, the modules developed across all project training tasks form a comprehensive and complementary training offer, allowing trainers to combine and adapt different modules or individual units to design tailored learning paths and training packages. **Each training module has a training outline** that clearly identifies the scope of the training, the learning objectives and target audience, the learning modalities, methodology and materials, as well as the learning assessment method. The training outline has been developed as a common approach for all training

materials and training-related deliverables in the project. The supporting materials include i) PowerPoint presentations prepared by the lecturers; ii) the recorded presentations; iii) other support learning materials such as videos, exercises, case studies etc. & iv) the training outline for each Module.

1. Learning needs assessment

1.1 General objectives

To define the general objective of the training programme to be designed, we started with the general objective of task 3.5: "Training on the production of high-quality organic seed". As its title suggests, the general objective of the training is to enable those involved in organic seed production to improve or maintain the quality of their organic seeds.

Seed germination and seedling establishment are the main factors for a successful start of a crop, determining crop health, weed suppression and overall crop performance. They are critical, but sensitive phases in crop production. Beyond mere germination rates, providing organic seeds that are vigorous is an important contribution to organic cropping systems. Providing your network or clients with seed of high physiological quality will contribute to their success in growing crops. Seed production practices, seed harvest and seed storage are important factors behind seed quality and vigour.

Seeds harbour microbial communities also called "seed microbiota". Together, they form an entity also called the "holobiont". Scientific research has shown that microbial species in the seed microbiota can play beneficial or detrimental roles in seed germination and seedling health for example. Many have neutral or yet unknown effects. Although yet unharnessed, this opens promising perspectives for organic seed production and cultivation. Sometimes, seed microbiota also comprise seed-borne pathogens, which can infect seedlings and jeopardise the following crop's health. When seed-transmitted diseases occur during seed propagation or in a seed lot, it is crucial to handle the situation with approaches and tools that are appropriate for organic farming.

Organic breeding and seed systems also hold innovative diversification strategies of crops and cultivars, such as heterogeneous population varieties, which are regulated under the legal term of Organic Heterogeneous Material (OHM). For some crops, such as cereals, organic breeding programmes also pioneer in breeding disease-resistant cultivars. This breeding innovations also come with special considerations and sometimes precautions for cultivation and propagation.

The training modules created in the frame of work package 3 of the Liveseeding project address all of these aspects of organic seed production, in the aim of supporting actors of organic seed production, in particular seed growers, farmers' seed networks, community seed banks and seed companies in their efforts to provide high quality, healthy seed as a basis for successful organic cropping systems.

These are the main actors managing seed quality and health. Of course, other, perhaps more specialised actors focussing on specific steps in the seed system – handling,

packaging, transport and distribution of example – also have a role to play in this management. However, their role is minor as compared to the actors cited above, and very specific. This is why they are not included in the target groups of the training modules.

1.2 Understanding the target audience

To begin developing the training programme, we based ourselves on the general objective of the training, which defines a "broad" target audience: those involved in seed production. We identified several types of stakeholders concerned by seed quality issues, defined by a combination of organisation types (farmer seed networks, community seed banks, large-scale seed companies, smaller scale seed companies) and a range of professions (farmers, facilitators or advisers and technicians supporting farmers).

	TARGET GROUP(S) 👤	EXISTING TRAINING PROGRAMM	
ÖMKI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 05 farmers saving seed - seed comp. → seed multipliers - low-input → find farmers to produce veg. seed - seed producers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X Not ÖMKI seed comp.? 	
ECLLD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 05 farmers / seed networks + community type of seed - seed savers (arable + veg.) - CSB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LLD nearby - LCB nearby ↳ organic holdings (arable + veg.) - plant + train the farmers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AgriNet ARCHE NOAH = resource
BSAG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - seed prod. + nurseries / breeders (veg.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X 1/ year 1 on summer sowing on 2 species crops internal + open SE! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - prod. seed (field/greenhouse) (seed intake in the interest?) - crop / seed health → documents available (instructions) + quality handbook 1 international workshop (on 1 crop?) in FR or NE?
PIN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - seed companies (SME) + their multipliers → conv. sowing can org. seed arable + veg. (comp. prod. for open hobby market) - open to the seed market 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X course for conv. seed prod. on seed collection 	
ITAB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - farmers seed networks - central multiplication veg. + arable. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X 	

Figure 1: Identification of target groups in a workshop carried out at the project kick-off meeting on 19 October 2022 in Zagreb.

Figure 2: continuation of the work on the target audience in an online workshop with task (3.5) partners on 14 February 2023.

Initial work on the target audience at the kick-off meeting on 19 October 2022 identified four categories of target audiences. These were refined by cross-referencing with three groups of critical skills identified following the kick-off meeting.

As illustrated in Figure 2, the Liveseeding training programme developed in task 3.5 is aimed at four categories of stakeholders.

- Farmers' seed networks and Community seed banks

In this category, **seed growers** are directly targeted by the training programme. In this context, farmers, gardeners and sometimes facilitation staff or volunteers manage seed quality and health all along the seed system from seed growing, cleaning, treating, handling to distribution. Each step requires specific equipment, knowledge and skills. These actors often have a rather agronomical training background, which does not cover in-depth background and practical knowledge in seed physiology and seed pathology, for example. For this stakeholder category, training is needed to complement existing knowledge and practice with relevant background knowledge and practical solutions to improve and/or ensure seed quality and health. This stakeholder group can either take self-paced e-learning modules directly, or their trainers or association staff may use the e-modules in more specific, blended-learning programmes for a farmers' seed network or Community Seed Bank.

- Contract seed producers

This category also includes **seed growers**, but their profile is slightly different from the previous ones. Unlike the previous group, they produce under contract for a seed company. In fact, they are often specialised in a few species and must meet quality criteria defined by the seed company, which may differ from those of the first group. Seed production often represents a significant part of their production activities, so they often have greater means of production than the previous group. They are not necessarily integrated into peer networks, but often benefit from the support of the seed company's technician. This stakeholder group does not have a need for knowledge and skills in the domains of fine seed sorting, handling, treatment and distribution, as these steps are managed by the seed company. Depending on their level of experience and background knowledge, they may benefit from training resources on seed physiology, especially regarding seed maturity, drying and cleaning. They may also be curious to widen their general knowledge about seeds, for example to know more about recent research on seed microbial communities and their roles in organic seed systems.

- Artisanal / small-scale seed enterprise

The last two groups are made up of advisers and technicians who support seed producers. The former work in small or medium-sized seed companies. Often working alone or in a team of two or three other technical staff, technical staff learn from each other but need to seek knowledge outside the seed company in order to continue to improve their skills. These types of seed enterprises often have limited resources and facilities for in-house research and development and therefore depend on public research and knowledge sharing as input for changing practices. Furthermore, these types of companies often operate in different markets from large firms, for example focussing on open-pollinated farmers' cultivars or local varieties, which come with specific constraints and require specific competencies. These staff generally need to have a broader expertise in a larger number of domains, as their work is less specialised than in large-scale or multinational companies.

Large-scale / multinational seed companies

Technical staff of large-scale or multinational seed companies often specialise in a restricted number of crops or fields of expertise. Operating in a large team, they are often highly skilled in their field, thanks to inhouse training and exchange and transfer of experience. In addition, these types of companies often have extended facilities and resources for research and development activities to support and guide technical staff in their practice. Advisors often work within a large team of advisors on an international scale. This reduces the need to seek knowledge from outside sources. This group of stakeholders is less dependent on external training and learning resources, but may find useful content in some of the modules and learning resources

especially if they lack experience in organic seed production. Companies may also use LiveSeeding's training modules when introducing new staff.

In addition to these four categories of actors, we have identified certain sub-categories:

- Organic and conventional producers

The training programme can indeed be aimed at both groups, but the former will already be familiar with the constraints inherent in organic production. For the latter, however, prior knowledge of the European specifications for organic farming will be a prerequisite.

- Novice versus expert seed producers

As for the previous section, the training programme can be aimed at both groups. However, it cannot be aimed at people who have no knowledge of seed production whatsoever; it is only aimed at stakeholders who are already involved in seed production or seed production consultancy. These stakeholders may be novices or experts. Depending on their level of expertise, they will choose the modules that meet their needs (basic modules and more advanced modules).

- Vegetable seed production versus cereal seed production

In terms of skills, for those involved in production (rather than advisors), starting seed production is a bigger step for a vegetable grower than for a cereal farmer. This is because cereal farmers are already involved in grain production. Although new knowledge is still required to manage harvesting, sorting and storage, these producers already have the basic equipment and knowledge. For market gardeners, the step is much bigger, as vegetable production is very different from grain production, especially for biannual vegetable species. In addition, the range of products is often much more diverse. A priori, they will therefore have a greater need for new knowledge and skills to start seed production.

1.3 Carrying out a task analysis

1.3.1 General approach

As part of a training course for professionals, we conducted a task analysis to identify the knowledge and skills that trainees should acquire to achieve the overall training objective defined above. Task analysis makes it possible to "create a work-centred training course that caters to different professional profiles, focuses on qualifications

and skills, and creates scenarios based on real cases that establish realistic work contexts" (FAO, 2021, page 33).

This task analysis was carried out by experts and only concerns those involved in production. We did not look at the tasks of advisors or technicians in the context of supporting producers who wish to maintain or improve the quality of their organic seeds. Nor did we analyse these tasks by interviewing those involved in production, as the experts who participated in this task analysis have a detailed knowledge of the profession.

<p>What is a task analysis?</p> <p>In the context of instructional design, a task analysis is a detailed analysis of actions and decisions that a person takes to perform a task, which includes identifying the knowledge needed to support those actions and decisions.</p>
<p>What is a task?</p> <p>A task is a unit of work that is accomplished in order to get a product, provide a service or obtain a result.</p>

Figure 3: Definition of a task and task analysis, excerpt from the guide "E-learning methodologies and good practices". (FAO, 2021, page 33)

Task analysis can be subdivided into several stages, as illustrated in the table below.

<p>STEP 1: INVENTORYING TASKS</p> <p>Identify the tasks that learners should learn or improve in, to achieve the desired performance outcome expressed by the course goal.</p> <p>For example: What tasks should analysts perform to produce quality analysis?</p>	<p>STEP 2: PRIORITIZING TASKS</p> <p>Usually, it is not feasible to develop training for each task involved in a job. From the identified tasks, select those that have priority in terms of criticality, frequency, or organization preference.</p> <p>These would be the tasks on which to focus the analysis and the development of the learning programme.</p>	<p>STEP 3: BREAKING UP THE TASKS</p> <p>Having decided which tasks to analyse further, break down selected tasks into their component parts.</p> <p>You will need to identify the operations (both observable and mental) required to complete the task.⁶</p> <p><small>⁶ See the book <i>Task Analysis Methods for Instructional Design</i> by D.H. Jonassen, M. Tessermer and W.H Hannum to learn more about task analysis process and functions and techniques used to perform task analysis.</small></p>	<p>STEP 4: IDENTIFYING REQUIRED KNOWLEDGE</p> <p>Identify the knowledge needed to perform the operations identified in the previous step, and that should be provided as part of the learning programme (Clark, 2007).</p>
---	---	---	---

Table 1: The stages of task analysis, excerpt from the guide "E-learning methodologies and good practices". (FAO, 2021, page 33).

The task analysis began at the kick-off meeting in 2022 and was completed in 2024. It comprised several stages:

- initial work in a workshop at the kick-off meeting in October 2022 enabled the critical tasks related to seed production, sorting and storage to work on.

Figure 4 : Identification of critical tasks during a workshop at the kick-off meeting on 19 October 2022.

- Following this initial workshop, we decided to continue our work by separating the exploration of post-harvest (higher priority) and pre-harvest tasks. A first version of the post-harvest task reference framework was presented to the partners of task 3.5 on 14 February 2023. This step enabled us to start benchmarking available training courses and resources on the post-harvest phase.
- Once the benchmarking was completed in 2023, we developed a reference framework for pre-harvest tasks in 2024. This framework was presented to task partners in an online workshop on 16 April 2024. At this workshop, the results of the benchmarking of available training courses and resources were also presented. This enabled us to prioritise the tasks in the reference framework on which the project should focus in order to develop one or more training programmes on the production of high quality, healthy seed.

Figure 5 : Screenshot showing the votes of the participants at the online workshop in April 2024. This prioritisation work was reported into a table

1.3.2 Results of the task analysis

The task reference framework is structured around five main task categories

Five main categories of tasks were identified regarding producers who are aiming to improve or maintain the quality of their organic seeds:

- **Plan and establish the seed crop**
- **Monitoring and managing the health of a seed crop**
- **Define an optimal harvesting and threshing or extraction strategy**
- **Define a sorting (cleaning), drying and storage strategy**
- **Define a strategy to obtain (and maintain) homogeneous seed lots of good quality in terms of germination and health: evaluate and correct**

The figure below shows these five categories and the respective associated sub-tasks. Within each of these sub-tasks, lower-level tasks have been identified. The complete mind map is included in the annex 1.

Figure 6: Task reference framework in the form of a mind map, reduced format

The figure below shows all the subtasks belonging to the category "define a strategy to obtain (and maintain) homogeneous seed lots of good quality in terms of germination and health: evaluate and correct".

Figure 7: For the category "define a strategy to obtain (and maintain) homogeneous seed lots of good quality in terms of germination and health: evaluate and correct", list of sub-tasks.

Setting priorities among tasks according to their criticality and the existing offer in terms of available knowledge and training

At the end of the workshop on 16 April 2024, the group had identified the tasks for which it was a priority for the LIVESEEDING project to design training programmes, because they are critical for the production of high-quality organic seeds and because there are few or no cognitive resources available to learn how to master the task.

Skill or field of competency	Vote (fr	Sub-skill level 1	Vote (from 2024 April Meeting)
Introduction		Distinguish and define the components of quality of organic seed	
1 >> Plan and establish the seed crop	3.4444	1.1 Identify the regulatory framework for your seed production	👉 4
		1.2 List the factors that can have an effect on seed quality and health throughout the crop cycle	👆 8
		1.3 Identify the characteristics and needs of the species and the cultivar (whether it was chosen by the seed producer or prescribed by the seed company)	👉 6
		1.4 Choose sowing or planting density	👇 1
		1.5 Choose sowing or planting date	👇 1
		1.6 Choose a plot to avoid cross-breeding	👉 3
		1.7 Choose and prepare a plot to ensure plant nutrition	👇 2
		1.8 Evaluate the risk of infection of the basic seed lot with seed transmitted diseases before sowing	👇 2
		1.9 Treat seed before sowing to prevent the risk of seed transmitted disease	👉 4
		2 >> Monitor and manage the health of a seed crop	5.2
Know which weeds are particularly problematic in a seed crop and control them	NO EVALUATION		
2.1 Identify and describe (diagnosis) a crop health problem	👆 9		
2.2 Evaluate possible consequences of a plant health issue and possible corrective measures	👉 6		
2.3 Plan and decide on a strategy to counter the problem	👉 3		
2.4 Implement measure to counter the problem	👉 6		
3 >> Define an optimal strategy to harvest and thresh or extract seed	3.75	1.1 Decide when and how to harvest	👆 7.5
		1.2 Implement the extraction or threshing method (if dissociated from plant harvest)	👇 0
4 >> Define a sorting and cleaning, drying and storing strategy in order to ensure the conservability of the seeds	6	2.1 Identify the state of a seed lot that is necessary for its conservation (accordingly, define the objective of seed cleaning and drying)	👉 5
		2.2 Choose the method and equipment to sort, dry and store seeds in order to ensure their conservation	👆 7
5 >> Define a strategy to obtain (and maintain) homogeneous seed lots of good quality in terms of germination and health	5	3.1 Finely sort and clean a seed lot to optimise quality (based on seed size, density, shape, colour)	👆 7
		3.2 Evaluate seed quality based on germination capacity	👇 2
		3.3 Evaluate seed health and/or have it analysed by a lab	👆 8
		3.4 Know and implement seed treatments to prevent/control seed transmitted diseases	NO EVALUATION
		3.5 Define a short or longer term strategy to sanitise a seed lot according to issue(s) identified	👆 7
		3.6 Improve the technological or germination quality of a seed lot (coating, priming)	👇 1

Table 2: Priorities set among the tasks and sub-tasks of the task reference framework.

For the first set of tasks, "Plan and establish the seed crop", two sub-tasks were identified as priorities:

- List the factors that can have an effect on seed quality and health throughout the crop cycle
- Identify the characteristics and needs of the species and the cultivar (whether it was chosen by the seed producer or prescribed by the seed company)

For the second group of tasks, "Monitor and manage the health of a seed crop", three sub-tasks were defined as priorities, and two were added by the 3.5 task leader:

- Know and implement general preventive measures against plant diseases
- Know which weeds are particularly problematic in a seed crop and control them
- Identify and describe (diagnosis) a crop health problem
- Evaluate possible consequences of a plant health issue and possible corrective measures
- Implement measures to counter the problem

Regarding the third set of tasks, "Define an optimal strategy to harvest and thresh or extract seed", only one task was selected: Decide when and how to harvest

With regard to the fourth group of tasks, "Define a sorting and cleaning, drying and storing strategy in order to ensure the conservability of the seeds", two tasks were identified as priorities:

- Identify the state of a seed lot that is necessary for its conservation (accordingly, define the objective of seed cleaning and drying)
- Choose the method and equipment to sort, dry and store seeds in order to ensure their conservation

Finally, concerning the fifth task group, "Define a strategy to obtain (and maintain) homogeneous seed lots of good quality in terms of germination and health", three sub-tasks were defined as priorities, and one was added by the 3.5 task leader.

- Finely sort and clean a seed lot to optimise quality (based on seed size, density, shape, colour)
- Evaluate seed health and/or have it analysed by a lab
- Know and implement seed treatments to prevent/control seed transmitted diseases
- Define a short- or longer-term strategy to sanitise a seed lot according to issue(s) identified

It was based on this material, in particular, that the LIVESEEDING training programme began taking shape.

2. Mapping and analysis of the existing training offer

2.1 General approach

As specified in the previous chapter, analysing the existing training offer is an integral part of training design. The choice of tasks to be explored in terms of training was guided not only by the task analysis described above, but also by the analysis of the

existing offer of available training courses and resources. The analysis of the existing offer concerns available "cognitive resources", which are either resources that can be downloaded (freed of charge or not) from knowledge portals (video brief; replay of virtual class, webinar, slideshow - presentation used in virtual class, webinar, various events, text documents - practice abstract, booklet, leaflet, guidelines - websites; books and reports, tools, databases, training support - quizzes, case studies, survey questionnaires and other exercises), or training courses. Analysing the offer also makes it possible to build a library of resources for designing training modules. As we will see later, this library has been used in the design of e-learning modules. It also helps to promote the LIVESEEDING training offer by highlighting the added value of programmes designed by the project compared to existing offerings. The benchmarking work began on 14 March 2023, once the task reference framework had been validated for post-harvest tasks. It was then updated on an ongoing basis.

Existing training courses and resources

<u>What is a training course ?</u>	<u>What is a training resource ?</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One or more training objectives formulated • Program, duration • Learning assessment • Targets, prerequisites • Can be splited in modules • Combine a variety of resources • Free or not free • Requires somebody to organize (or support) the training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An entity, digital or not, used in a learning process • One or several authors • Used alone, is not enough to make people learn • Knowledge formulated, described (video, text, infographic, etc.) or learning activity support (survey questionnaire, quiz, case study, etc.)

Figure 8 : instructions given to task 3.5 partners to carry out the benchmarking of available training courses and resources.

Although the benchmarking work continued after April 2024, an analysis of this benchmarking work was presented in a workshop on 16 April 2024. The results are presented in the following two paragraphs.

2.2 Results

2.2.1 Existing training courses

Although the benchmark we conducted is not exhaustive (it mainly covers Poland, the Netherlands and France), we identified no less than 39 training programmes in these three countries relating to seed production, storage and sorting. These training

courses do not exclusively concern organic seeds but are relevant for organic seed production.

- **Five academic courses** for students or researchers, lasting from one semester to two years: two in Poland, two in France and one in the Netherlands. These long courses cover a wide range of topics: "Plant breeding and seed production" in Poland, "Seeds and seedlings" in France and "Seed Science and Technology" in the Netherlands.
- **Two independent e-learning courses**, non-certifying: one is offered by the Organic Seed Alliance¹ in the United States and focuses exclusively on organic seed production. It aims to provide useful knowledge for professional seed growers, as does the LIVESEEDING training programme. The other training programme is a MOOC (Massive Online Open Course) offered by the "AgroRennesAngers" higher education school of agronomy. This training programme covers seeds in general² and is aimed at people who have no previous knowledge in the field of seeds. The aim is to understand the issues and scopes of seed production and sales around the world. Unlike the online training offered by OSA, this programme does not focus on professional skills.
- Finally, the benchmarking exercise identified 33 vocational training programmes in the context of continuing education (1 in the United States, 2 in the Netherlands and 31 in France)
 - Three are offered by CFPPAs in France (adult vocational training centres) that train **future farmers**. These courses lead to a qualification and are an integral part of the BPREA (*Brevet Professionnel Responsable d'Entreprise Agricole* - Professional Certificate in Agricultural Business Management). They last 70 hours. They are not specific to organic farming and cover the basics of seed production and storage.
 - Eight are offered by the *Réseau Semences Paysannes*³ and two by organic farming groups. These training courses for independent producers last an average of 1.5 days and are non-certifying. They are short training courses for on-farm seed production (as a complement to main production: arable crops or vegetables). They cover the basics of producing and storing farm-saved or organic seeds and are aimed at active **producers who have never produced seeds before**.
 - Sixteen training courses are offered by SEMAE⁴, the French Interprofessional Organisation for Seeds and Plants, or GEVES⁵ - the French Variety and Seed Study and Control Group. These training courses are mainly aimed at **small, medium and large seed companies and more specifically at certain professions**: crop manager, crop protection

¹ [Organic Seed Alliance - Putting the power of seed into the hands of growers](#)

² [Plant seeds: what are the challenges for our future? - Course - FUN MOOC](#)

³ [Réseau Semences Paysannes - Accueil](#)

⁴ <https://www.semae.fr/en/> and <https://formation.semae.fr/asfis-training-programs>

⁵ <https://www.geves.fr/training-at-geves/>

manager, seed treatment manager, laboratory manager, company manager, etc. These are advanced training courses in sorting, cleaning and seed analysis, but not in organic farming. The only module on organic farming deals with regulation. Seed production is touched upon briefly in a module on agroecological production. These courses do not lead to certification and last approximately two days.

- Four professional training programmes are offered by ITAB, ITAB-WUR, and Sorbonne University. These training programmes are aimed at **advisors, trainers, seed company technicians, and researchers**. They last an average of 2.5 days. These are advanced training courses in seed biology and quality for trainers and researchers. Only the Liveseeding training is specific to organic agriculture. There is also an ITAB training course on the management of common bunt in wheat in organic farming.

For the detailed results of this benchmarking exercise, see the annexes 3 and 4. It should be noted that it is difficult to carry out a benchmark when the structure of the training provision in a country is unknown. Indeed, no website lists all the training courses available. It is necessary to visit the websites of each training organisation "known to have expertise in seeds" to check the existence of continuing education programmes. While a detailed search of the training offer was carried in France by an expert in training design, task partners collected training courses in their respective countries, as well as they could according to their level of skill. This resulted in a longer list of available training courses in France than in other partner countries. However, when results were presented, task 3.5 partners not surprised by the findings, as France is one of the European countries where the Agricultural Knowledge Innovation System (AKIS) for seeds is most developed.

2.2.2 Conclusion on the offer of existing training courses

The short vocational training courses we identified cover pre- and post-harvest stages, but not much on overall quality management. We did not find anything specifically related to quality management in organic farming. We therefore conclude that there is room for training aimed at expert audiences (growers or technicians in small-scale companies) focusing on seed quality management, in the field and after harvest, specific to organic farming.

2.2.3 Learning resources available on knowledge portals and other websites

The resource benchmark identified a total of 82 resources: freely accessible text documents, chargeable text documents such as books, showcases and kits, videos and webinar replays, and digital tools. The majority of these resources are available in

English (50 out of 82). Twenty-five are only available in French, one in Hungarian, one in Polish and five in German.

It should be noted that the two organisations providing the most learning resources are: Organic Seed Alliance (USA) - 18 resources identified - and SEMAE (FR) - 12 resources identified. The Liveseed project also appears to be an important source of knowledge on organic seed production (7 resources identified), as does the FNAMS⁶, (French National Federation of Seed Multipliers) with 5 resources identified. **These 4 organisations or projects (OSU, SEMAE, Liveseeding, FNAMS) account for more than 50% of the resources identified.**

After identifying all these resources, we began **sorting and prioritising them** on 16 April 2024. Participating task 3.5 partners gave their opinion on the relevance of each of these resources. An analysis of the resources based on the task reference framework was also carried out. Following this two-way analysis, a list of **11 priority resources was drawn up**. They are listed in the table below.

Resource title	Source	Language
Infographics: Alveolar sorter, cleaner-separator, densimetric table, optical sorter, sorting & treating line	SEMAE	FR
Climatic Considerations for Seed Crops: Guidelines and Field Trainings for Organic and Specialty Vegetable Seed Producers	OSA	EN
Crop specific leaflets and videos on the seed production of many crops; including specific leaflets on organic seed production for: lentils, onions, squash (zucchini), carrot, coriander, cabbages, lettuce, bean, chickpea	FNAMS, ITAB	FR
General principles of organic seed production	FNAMS, ITAB	FR
Meadow plants: sorting seeds of forage crops (Plantes pairiales : triage des semences fourragères)	SEMAE	FR
Practical guide: Organic cereal seed production (Guide pratique - Produire des semences de céréales en agriculture biologique)	FNAMS	FR
Practical guide: Seed harvest (Guide pratique - La récolte des semences)	FNAMS	FR
Seed Quality: Best Practices for Vegetable Seed Handling in Montana	OSA	EN

⁶ [Fédération Nationale des Agriculteurs Multiplicateurs de Semences - Fnams](#)

Organic Seed Resource Guide	eOrganic	EN
Guidelines for testing the quality of farm-saved vegetable seed / Leitfaden zur Qualitätsprüfung von On-farm erzeugtem Saatgut von Gemüsearten	Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, VERN	DE
Infographic: Seed and Plant Health: A continuum / Qualité des semences et Santé des Plantes : un continuum / Saatgut-und Pflanzengesundheit : ein Kontinuum	Itab, WUR / LiveSeeding	EN, FR, DE

Table 3: resources identified as priorities for organic high-quality seed production by task 3.5 partners

This benchmarking work has been an important resource for the design of the training modules. It also constitutes a library that will be shared directly in the LIVESEEDING project with all project target groups.

3. Offering methodological support to training designers

In order to support task 3.5 and all project partners in developing high-quality training programmes, the task leader (ITAB) implemented a dual approach.

3.1 Training engineering

At regular task 3.5 meetings, the task leaders explained the training engineering approach used to design the training programmes. Several tools were also developed to assist training programme designers in their work, including a reflexivity grid to support trainer training (see next chapter), an evaluation grid for training prototypes that 4 partners developed and implemented, and a tool to assist in the design of learning activities for a workshop held during the project annual meeting in September 2024. Resources were also shared, including the FAO Guide to Designing Online Training Modules, second edition. This support was made available to all LIVESEEDING project stakeholders through the organisation of a webinar in 2023 on the design of a teaching scenario, and to all project partners at the 2024 annual meeting on the design of training modules.

Tools

The reflection grid on training trainers in organic seed production, training tool evaluation survey, and learning situation design tool for task 3.5 - are available in the annex 5.

3.2 Trainers' training on seed harvest, drying and storage for organic seed production

To support project partners in designing training programmes on the management of physiological seed quality in organic seed production and to ensure to provide the same level of basic knowledge of the subject, a training course was organised in April 2023 in Wageningen. Reserved for project partners, particularly those involved in Task 3.5, it aimed to draw on the renowned expertise of Steven Groot, Professor in Seed Physiology, before his retirement.

Figure 9: Steven Groot (WUR), speaker at the training of trainers course held in Wageningen on 4 and 5 April 2023 (photo credit: Stephanie Klaedtke)

Programme

Seed development and maturation

- Pollen, fertilisation and seed set
- Seed filling, maturation and protection; Chlorophyll and seed maturity
- Sensitivity of seeds to sanitation treatments
- Seed shattering and prevention; Dormancy and preharvest sprouting
- Slow-drying systems upon harvest

Seed Drying

- Why drying is needed and seed drying tolerance of species
- Seed drying methods and psychrometric chart
- Moisture diffusion and drying rates
- Seed moisture content versus Relative Humidity and their analysis

Seed Storage

- Seed ageing, other quality losses during storage and type of damage
- Effect of moisture, temperature and oxygen on ageing
- Control of storage conditions, data loggers
- Storage of germplasm and breeding lines
- Invigoration treatments (priming, humidification) and storage of primed seeds

Figure 10: programme of the two-day trainers' training course

The detailed programme is presented **in the annex 6**.

This trainers' training was attended by 12 participants representing 11 organisations from 10 European countries. From the feedback given by participants, at least 5 of the participating organisations have since held courses based on the training content, either internal to their organisation or external ones. Five organisations have also provided evidence that participating in the course has led to changes in the way they monitor seed drying and storage.

As a general assessment of the course, 10 participants rated their satisfaction at 10/10, one participant 9/10 and one participant 7/10. As regarding the 3 learning objectives of the course, all participants answered "rather yes" or "yes" to the question "At the end of the course, tell us to what extent you have achieved the objectives". One participant answered "no" regarding one of the learning objectives ("Optimise seed production, obtain and maintain higher seed quality").

This course has led to the organisation of specific workshops at the three "Let's Liberate Diversity" Fora held by the European Coordination "Let's Liberate Diversity" in Ireland (2023), France (2024) and Luxembourg (2025). It also made way to the publication of a Practical Guide by several project partners, which is available on

Organic Farm Knowledge⁷ and has been downloaded 5500 times by September 2025 and forms part of Module 13 on Seed Drying and Storage.

4. Development of the Liveseeding training material

To ensure training materials would stay available and useable after the end of the project, it was decided to develop an online, self-paced training programme. In the following paragraph, we will outline the characteristics of self-paced learning among all distance learning methods and the reasons behind our choice.

4.1 The choice of self-paced learning

4.1.1 Definition

E-learning is the use of electronic devices and Internet technologies to deliver a variety of solutions to enable learning and improve performance” (FAO, 2021, p. IV). It can be simple technological solutions

E-learning courses are stand-alone interactive learning materials that correspond to one or more learning objectives by providing explanations, examples, interactivity, questions and feedback, glossaries, etc., in order to make learners self-sufficient in learning new concepts and skills. They can combine several types of media, including text, images, animations, audio and video.

E-learning courses can include one or more e-learning lessons, whose duration should be limited to a maximum of about 30 minutes of learning time.

	Self-paced e-learning	Facilitated e-learning	Virtual classroom
Features	Alone - No social interaction with trainer, facilitator or trainees - Fully asynchronous	Alone or with others - Interaction at least with a “facilitator”, presupposes the presence of a third party, and therefore a certain synchronicity (within a given period).	Several. Social interaction with trainer and possibly trainees. Fully synchronous
Advantages and limitations	More “flexible” for the trainee - “easier” to disseminate on a	Between the two, advantages of both	Less “flexible” for the trainee (defined date and time) - less audience, but much

⁷ <https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/52128> epri

	massive scale BUT takes longer to prepare because it must fully integrate facilitation (accompanying resources must be created).		shorter preparation time. The trainer takes care of managing interaction, assessing learning, introducing the course, questioning trainees, etc.
--	--	--	--

Table 4: comparison of self-paced learning, facilitated e-learning, virtual classroom, from FAO, 2021.

4.1.2 Why self-paced learning?

Self-paced learning has the advantage of being able to reach a very wide audience in terms of time and space. Delivered in English, our e-learning modules can be taken by anyone who understands English. Available asynchronously at any time and requiring no interaction with others (peers or a facilitator), e-learning modules can be taken anywhere under any conditions (provided a good internet connection is available to watch the videos).

Beyond this advantage, self-paced learning also allows knowledge produced within and thanks to the LIVESEEDING project to be shared beyond the duration of the project. Indeed, it often happens that the sharing of knowledge from a project stops when the project ends. Here, the decision was made to make resources directly available to the target audience, hosted on a project partner's website (rather than directly on the project website) to facilitate updates once the project has ended.

It should be noted, however, that self-paced learning has one limitation: it does not allow all types of skills to be developed. It mainly targets cognitive skills (understanding, synthesising, etc.). In fact, for the acquisition of professional skills (necessary for practice), e-learning can only constitute a foundation that must be supplemented by other training activities, some of which are face-to-face, allowing participants to put their skills into practice through internships or simply through practical experience.

Can e-learning be used to develop any type of skill?

Training programmes aim to develop different types of skills:

COGNITIVE SKILLS, which involve increasing knowledge and comprehension (e.g. scientific concepts), following instructions (i.e. procedural skills) and applying methods in new situations to solve problems (i.e. thinking or strategic skills);

INTERPERSONAL SKILLS, such as those involved in active listening, presenting or negotiating; and

PSYCHOMOTOR SKILLS, which involve acquiring physical perceptions and movements (e.g. playing sports or driving a car).

How can e-learning address these diverse domains?

Most e-learning courses are developed to build cognitive skills; the cognitive domain is the most suitable for e-learning. Within the cognitive domain, strategic skills may require more interactivity because those skills are learned better 'by doing'.

Learning in the interpersonal domain can also be addressed in e-learning by using specific methods. For example, online collaboration activities or interactive role playing with appropriate feedback can be used to change attitudes and behaviours.

Table 5: excerpt from page 4 of the FAO Guide, skills developed through e-learning

These e-learning courses have therefore been designed to be taken either independently and individually, separate from any training programme, or as part of other more comprehensive training programmes, such as "blended learning".

Why design a self-paced learning module ?

Blended courses =

E-learning + face to face learning +/- learning at work

E-learning is used :

- Before
- Follow-up to
- Before and after

A face-to-face event

3rd Annual General Meeting & GA
Novara, Poznan, 17-20 Sept 2024

Figure 11 : extract from a presentation given at the annual meeting in September 2024: place of an e-learning module in a blended learning programme.

4.2 Basic pedagogical structure of our e-learning courses

Expository teaching method

To facilitate the training design for project partners who are not specialists in training engineering, we have chosen to teach trainees **using the expository method**. These methods are easy to implement as they are based on the creation of commented presentations, a task that the engineers and researchers involved in the LIVESEEDING project are already familiar with. Furthermore, these methods are also simple for trainees, as they only require them to listen and understand, and to have basic computer equipment for watching videos and answering quizzes, tasks that many trainees are now familiar with (unlike the use of online whiteboards or other more complex tools).

Expositive methods – which emphasize the ‘absorption’ of new information. Expositive methods include presentations, case studies, worked examples and demonstrations.

Application methods – which emphasize the active processes that learners use to perform procedural and principle-based tasks and build new knowledge. Application methods include the demonstration-practice method, job aids, case-based or scenario-based exercises, role play, simulations and serious games, guided research and project work.

Collaborative methods – which emphasize the social dimension of learning and engage learners in sharing knowledge and performing tasks in a collaborative way. They include online guided discussions, collaborative work and peer tutoring.

Table 6: excerpt from the FAO guide, 2021, page 51, teaching methods for e-learning

The e-learning modules on the production of high-quality organic seeds all have the same structure

- One or more short videos, based on a slideshow with audio commentary by the author.
- A quiz consisting of an average of five questions, with feedback so that the quiz contributes to constructive assessment. These questions are true/false, multiple choice, or ranking in order.
- Additional resources for further study, often from the library built up in the benchmarking phase
- Possibly an application exercise allowing to test a practice covered in the course on a small scale (e.g. treating seeds with hot water).

In order to give a human face to these e-learning tools, which require trainees to work alone at their computers, each module is introduced by a photo of the trainer, a short presentation of their background, and a reminder of the challenges and training objectives of the module. **Eight modules have been designed in this way.**

Finally, to enable trainees to progress in their learning, the modules have been linked together by three different pathways:

- [Learning Path #1] Ensuring seed quality when propagating and storing seed (modules 11, 12, 13, 14)
- [Learning Path #2] Ensuring organic seed health: tools to understand and manage (modules 11, 14, 15, 18)
- [Learning Path #3] Getting to know and tracking organic heterogeneous material (modules 16 and 17)

Trainees can therefore enter directly via a learning pathway, or enter a module and be directed to other modules from their pathway.

4.3 Hosting the e-modules and providing a user interface

The LIVESEEDING project did not provide for the design of a dedicated e-learning training interface. As the modules designed are free and accessible to all, we chose to make them available on a standard website, guiding learners as best as possible in their navigation. The choice was between hosting the e-learning modules on the LIVESEEDING project website or on the ITAB website. With a view to facilitating updates after the project, the training modules on the production of healthy, high quality organic seeds were implemented on the ITAB website, with links from the LIVESEEDING website.

5. Presentation of the e-learning space and associated resources

Dedicated e-learning space: [E-learning training on Seed Quality Production | ITAB](#)

5.1 Introduction & link to the task reference framework

The training design process described in the previous sections resulted in a task reference framework. Priorities were set among the set of skills with expert project partners to identify the ones that need to be addressed by the project's training material.

To avoid putting project efforts into duplicating already existing resources and concentrate on filling training gaps, priority tasks were compared with the lists of available training courses (Annex 3) and resources (Annex 4). This allowed to identify

- (i) relevant and unique resources recommended for translation into other languages as a training resource. For example, a French practical guide on organic cereal seed production by FNAMS⁸ was recommended for translation to Polish and Hungarian.
- (ii) Learning resources which can feed into training modules as reading material or additional resource. For example, a booklet on Organic Heterogeneous Material published by Seeds4All⁹ is a suggested additional resource for Module 16, as is a presentation given by Rete Semi Rurale in the frame of a past project, LIVESEED.
- (iii) Topics and target audiences of Training Modules to be produced by the Liveseeding project.

For the training modules, many of the topics identified as priority were covered by the expertise and competencies of project partners involved in Work Package 3. Project partners, existing learning resources and novel project publications were this combined in 8 new training modules. These training modules were combined to form “learning paths” with specific learning objectives and target audiences.

5.2 Presentation of learning paths and e-learning modules

5.2.1 Learning paths

Learning paths have been designed to link the specific objectives of each training module with the task reference framework. Three learning paths have been created:

[Learning Path #1] Ensuring seed quality when propagating and storing seed

Scope

Seed germination and seedling establishment are the main factors for a successful start of a crop, determining crop health, weed suppression and overall crop performance. They are critical, but sensitive phases in crop production. Beyond mere germination rates, providing organic seeds that are vigorous is an important contribution to organic cropping systems. Providing your network or clients with seed of high physiological quality will contribute to their success in growing crops. Seed production practices, seed harvest and seed storage are important factors behind seed quality and vigour.

Seeds are also associated with microbial communities called the seed microbiota. Scientific research has shown that microbial species in the seed microbiota can play beneficial or detrimental roles in seed germination and seedling health for example. Many have neutral or yet unknown effects. Although yet unharnessed, this opens

⁸ <https://fnams.fr/produire-des-semences-de-cereales-en-agriculture-biologique/>

⁹ https://liberatediversity.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/OHM_Booklet_S4A.pdf

promising perspectives for organic seed production and cultivation. An optional module offers an introduction into this fascinating topic, as an outlook into another aspect of seed quality.

Target audience:

- Seed producers, seed networks and community seed banks, who want to train their staff or members to ensure the physiological quality of the seed they produce and distribute and to optimise the conservation of their seeds through seed drying and storage conditions.
- Beginning small-scale organic seed enterprises, willing to market high quality, reliable organic seed right from the start
- Advisors of organic seed producing farms willing to support their clients in ensuring optimal quality of the seed produced.

Associated modules : 11, 12, 13 et 14

Link : <https://itab.bio/en/elearningseedproduction/LearningPath1>

[Learning Path #2] Ensuring organic seed health : tools to understand and manage

Scope

Seeds harbour microbial communities also called “seed microbiota”. Together, they form an entity also called the “holobiont”. Scientific research has shown that microbial species in the seed microbiota can play beneficial or detrimental roles in seed germination and seedling health for example. Many have neutral or yet unknown effects. Although yet unharnessed, this opens promising perspectives for organic seed production and cultivation. Sometimes, seed microbiota also comprise seed-borne pathogens, which can infect seedlings and jeopardise the following crop’s health. When seed-transmitted diseases occur during seed propagation or in a seed lot, it is crucial to handle the situation with approaches and tools that are appropriate for organic farming.

This training course gives an overview of seed quality and health and how they are intertwined. It provides a general understanding of seed microbiota, how they assemble and how they are studied for research purposes. It also presents specific approaches to ensure seed health in vegetable and wheat seed production.

Target audience:

- Seed producers, seed networks and community seed banks, who want to train their staff or members to ensure the health of the seed they produce and distribute and who want to gain a better understanding and confidence in the field of seed health.
- Beginning small-scale organic seed enterprises, who need to get familiar with the management of seed health in organic farming systems
- Advisors of organic seed producing farms willing to support their clients in seed health.

Associated modules: 11, 14, 15, 18

Link : <https://itab.bio/en/elearningseedproduction/LearningPath2>

[Learning Path #3] Getting to know and tracking Organic heterogeneous material

Scope

Organic heterogeneous material (OHM) is a new legal category created in the framework of the EU organic regulation (EU) 2018/848) to enable the marketing of seed of heterogeneous populations. Heterogeneous crops in general, and OHM in particular, has several advantages for organic cropping systems, as compared to homogeneous varieties. It requires some specific considerations in seed propagation. From an administrative perspective, putting OHM seed on the market follows a specific notification procedure and requires tracking seed lots. This training course gives insights into OHM, its advantages and seed propagation, as well as a practical introduction to OHMTrack, a digital tool for notifying and tracking OHM.

Another training module offered by the Liveseeding project deals in more detail with the notification of OHM, it is available.

Target audience:

- Organic plant breeders or plant breeders with an interest in organic breeding, willing to get acquainted with the topic of OHM
- Seed companies propagating and marketing OHM
- Organic plant breeders or staff of national authorities managing OHM who need to be trained to use the OHMTrack tool.

Associated modules: 16 et 17

Link: <https://itab.bio/en/elearningseedproduction/LearningPath3>

5.2.2 The modules

Eight modules have been designed, according to the structure specified above. The links to the training material are listed in the table 7 below. The ITAB link provides full materials and guidance for self-paced learners as well as some extra exercises and further reading, while on Organic E-Print there are the training materials (powerpoints, quiz, etc).

Table 7: Links to module webpages hosted on the ITAB website

Module	Link to the module webpage on ITAB website and Organic eprints	Learning path
Module 11: General introduction to organic seed quality & health	https://itab.bio/en/elearningseedproduction/Module11	1, 2
Module 12: Seed maturity and harvest	https://itab.bio/en/elearningseedproduction/Module12	1
Module 13: Seed drying and storage	https://itab.bio/en/elearningseedproduction/Module13	1
Module 14: An introduction to seed microbiota	https://itab.bio/en/elearningseedproduction/Module14	1, 2
Module 15: Hot water treatments for the sanitation of vegetable seeds	https://itab.bio/en/elearningseedproduction/Module15	2
Module 16: OHM, General introduction, seed production and traceability	https://itab.bio/en/elearningseedproduction/Module16	3
Module 17: Tracking OHM, a digital tool for the notification, traceability of OHM seed	https://itab.bio/en/elearningseedproduction/Module17	3

Module 18: Growing and propagating bunt resistant wheat varieties	https://itab.bio/en/elearningseedproduction/Module18	2
---	---	---

5.3 Appropriation of resources and framing of rules of use: choice of CC licence

In order to facilitate the appropriation of our training modules, particularly for trainers or facilitators who would like to integrate them into training courses or farmers' support programmes, we have chosen to use a Creative Commons licence. These licences allow us to specify what users can do with the resource without having to systematically seek permission from the author.

For our e-learning course on quality seed production, we have chosen a CC BY-NC-SA licence. This licence allows users to transform the material into another resource but prohibits doing so for commercial purposes and requires the new resource to be licensed under the same licence. The only use prohibited by this licence is commercial use, except a collective authorisation for all the module authors, of course. The entire set of e-learning modules belongs to all the authors of this deliverable. The author consortium is defined as the author and therefore the owner of these e-learning modules.

Definition of the CC BY-NC-SA Licence

This license enables reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format for noncommercial purposes only, and only so long as attribution is given to the creator. If you remix, adapt, or build upon the material, you must license the modified material under identical terms. CC BY-NC-SA includes the following elements: BY: credit must be given to the creator. NC: Only non-commercial uses of the work are permitted. SA: Adaptations must be shared under the same terms.

Bibliography

FAO. 2021. E-learning methodologies and good practices: A guide for designing and delivering e-learning solutions from the FAO elearning Academy, second edition. Rome.

Annexes

Annex 1: Mind map of key tasks for the production of high-quality, healthy organic seed

Annex 2: Task reference framework with priority vote

Skill or field of competency	Sub-skill level 1	Vote	Sub-skill level 2
Introduction	Distinguish and define the components of quality of organic seed		Define and characterise physiological seed quality (germination rate and seed vigour)
			Define and characterise seed health
			Define and characterise genetic quality aspects of seed lots (specific and varietal purity)
1 >> Plan and establish the seed crop	1.1_Identify the regulatory framework for your seed production	4	Identify the constraints on seed production in European and national regulations
			Identify the constraints on seed production in multiplication contracts with a seed company
	1.2_List the factors that can have an effect on seed quality and health throughout the crop cycle	8	
	1.3_Identify the characteristics and needs of the species and the cultivar (whether it was chosen by the seed producer or prescribed by the seed company)	6	List the pieces of information to gather on the species and the cultivar before sowing
1.4_Choose sowing or planting density	1	Know the effect that sowing or planting density may have on the risk of plant disease outbreaks	
		Know the effect that sowing or planting density may have on physiological seed quality	

	1.5_Choose sowing or planting date	1	Identify the different requirements in terms of sowing time in relation to plant growth and physiology for vegetable versus seed production (e.g. carrot, cabbages)
			Decide when to sow or plant a seed crop depending on the context
	1.6_Choose a plot to avoid cross-breeding	3	List the 3 aspects by which to evaluate a plot as regards the risk of cross-breeding: Minimal distance to others plots with the interfertile species, preceding crops and volunteers, wild plants (carrot)
			Evaluate the risk of cross-breeding for a given crop in a given plot.
	1.7_Choose and prepare a plot to ensure plant nutrition	2	List the 3 main aspects to take into account to optimise plant nutrition of the crop: Preceding crop and fertilisation, irrigation, soil fertility
		Evaluate the nutritional potential of a given plot for a given seed crop	
	1.8_Evaluate the risk of infection of the basic seed lot with seed transmitted diseases before sowing	2	1.8.a - List and know how to evaluate criteria to evaluate this risk : species (susceptibility to different diseases), seed source (reliability)
	1.9_Treat seed before sowing to prevent the risk of seed transmitted disease	4	1.9.a - Know how to conduct treatments
2 > > Monitor and manage the health of a seed crop	2.0_Know and implement general preventive measures against plant diseases		Know the general agronomic practices that favour plant health in organic farming
			Implement agronomic practices that favour general plant health in organic farming
	2.1_Identify and describe (diagnosis) a crop health problem	9	List available sources of information available to diagnose a crop health problem (lab analysis, technical consultants, web databases, etc.)
			Know how to distinguish plant disease symptoms from a nutrient deficiency
			Know how to observe the seed crop: According to species, when and where (plant parts) to observe?

			Recognise a plant disease issue based on symptoms and other sources of information
	2.2_Evaluate possible consequences of a plant health issue and possible corrective measures	6	Describe the propagation potential (mechanism and speed) of a plant disease and the possible affect on the crop Evaluate the growth stage/season at which the disease/pest occurs and establish a prognosis at plot level Situating your personal disease acceptability (threshold), taking into account legal requirements and the severity of plant disease in the plot. List possible interventions or treatments to correct un plant health problem in the seed crop Know if a diagnosed plant diseases it seed transmitted List the different seed treatments available against a given disease to sanitise seed
	2.3_Plan and decide on a strategy to counter the problem	3	Evaluate the risk-benefit ratio of a treatment or intervention in the field, if available Evaluate the risk-benefit ratio of a seed treatment after harvest, if available Evaluate the risk-benefit ratio of pursuing a long term strategy of seed sanitation, and maybe improving resistance/tolerance through selection Decide which measures to implement to counter a plant health issue in a given seed crop.
	2.4_Implement measure to counter the problem	6	Know how to implement a culling strategy in a seed crop Know how to implement a seed treatment after harvest, and/or how to report on the disease issue. Know of to implement a long term strategy for sanitation (or a strategy to select for greater tolerance/resistance to the disease)

	2.5_If nutrient deficiency or other physiological problem: learn how to prevent it in future crops.	2	Evaluate the risk-benefit ratio of correcting a nutrient deficiency, for example by fertilising with quick N fertilisers or micronutrients????
3 >> Define an optimal strategy to harvest and thresh or extract seed	1.1_Decide when and how to harvest	7.5	11a_Identify the maturity stage of a seed
			11b_Identify the maturity stage at the plant and field level
			11c_Identify and take into account the other factors (weather conditions, availability of equipment and labour force) to decide on the optimal time for harvest
			11d_Make a decision taking into account a combination of factors
			11e_Be aware of the different harvesting methods available, the possible types of equipment and their (dis)advantages The method depends on the crop species >> a specific module may be necessary for trainees who are founding an activity or those who a extending and existing farming activity, to be defined.
	1.2_Implement the extraction or threshing method (if dissociated from plant harvest)	0	12a_Evaluate the moisture rate in the harvested material (by touch) - critical especially for large seeds which break at threshing if too dry.
			12b_Implement the extraction process (fermentation), identify the risks of extracting too early or too late in the fermentation process
			12c_Identify the stage of the fermentation process to optimise seed extraction
4 >> Define a sorting and cleaning, drying and storing strategy in order to ensure the	2.1_Identify the state of a seed lot that is necessary for its conservation (accordingly, define the objective of seed cleaning and drying)	5	21a_Know the state of a seed lot that is necessary for its conservation in terms of cleanliness and purity.
			21b_Know the state of a seed lot that is necessary for its conservation in terms of moisture level.
	2.2_Choose the method and equipment to sort, dry and store seeds in order to ensure their conservation	7	22a_Choose the method and equipment to sort, dry and store seeds in order to ensure their conservation
5 ^ ^ D e		7	31a_Know the physical properties based on which one can sort seeds

	3.1_Finely sort and clean a seed lot to optimise quality (based on seed size, density, shape, colour)		31b_Choose the cleaning or sorting equipment available based on the physical properties according to which seed should be sorted	
			31c_Decide which fraction of a seed lot to keep (sorting threshold)	
	3.2_Evaluate seed quality based on germination capacity	2		32a_Know the criteria for assessing seed quality based on germination (including relevant regulations)
				32b_Choose the method and material for germination testing: the substrate, the container and conditions (temperature and humidity)
				32c_Interpret the results of a germination test, in particular differentiate between normal and abnormal seedlings
	3.3_Evaluate seed health and/or have it analysed by a lab	8		33a_Know the criteria to evaluate seed health, including those necessary for obtaining plant passport (European Plant Health regulation and seed regulations)
				33b_Identify a seed health issue based on symptoms observed in the seed crop or on germination tests
				33c_Decide whether a (costly) lab analysis should be conducted, based on field observations, germination tests and current regulations
				33d_Know and choose a service provider for lab analysis
	3.4_Know and implement seed treatments to prevent/control seed transmitted diseases			34a_List the categories of seed treatments available for organic seed
			34b_Know the advantages, disadvantages and risks of the different categories of treatments	
			34c_Implement some seed treatments and know about service providers for some others	
		7	35a_According to issue and crop species, know the sanitation methods available for organic seeds	

	3.5_Define a short or longer term strategy to sanitise a seed lot according to issue(s) identified		35b_According to the plant and seed history of the seed lot, as well as required techniques and equipment, decide to implement a sanitation strategy
			35c_Adapt the sanitation method to the initial quality of a seed lot to preserve its germination capacity, according to the sanitation objective (e.g. based on type of seed: elite, base or commercial)
	3.6_Improve the technological or germination quality of a seed lot (coating, priming)	1	36a_Know the specificities of each technique and its expected effects
			36b_Identify for which seed lots a respective technique is useful (crop species, initial quality)
			36c_Implement techniques - procedures and equipment

Annex 3: List and description of existing training courses, outcome of the benchmarking process

Title	Length	Date	Certificate or diploma	Training provider	Link to a presentation web page	Type of training	Main target (1 or 2 at most)
Biological Basis of seed quality : seeds of lignous shrubs (BASES BIOLOGIQUES DE LA QUALITÉ DES SEMENCES : GRAINES DE LIGNEUX ARBUSTIFS)	11 heures		NO	Campus Pierre et Marie Curie - Jussieu / Sorbonne Université	https://fc.sorbonne-universite.fr/nos-offres/bases-biologiques-de-la-qualite-des-semences-graines-de-ligneux-arbustifs/	Vocational	
Biology, Quality and seed technologies	21 heures	December 2023, then 2024	NO	Sorbonne Université	https://fc.sorbonne-universite.fr/nos-offres/biologie-qualite-et-technologies-des-semences/	Vocational	Technicians, engineers, researchers and breeders from seed seed producers and users. Agricultural advisors. Technical center staff.
Common bunt in organic farming: understanding to prevent and manage it	one day	2022	NO	ITAB, France	https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/e/2PACX-1vTgyaA9qTwtmJclUWhquNkcZx2Ly3IOJItNNvAXVq2fEZZIJaDWOQYISC_ppiVM3uqc6gSYXbZoDLeU/pub?start=false&loop=false&delayms=3000&slide=id.g993ee7f22f06	Vocational training (adult and professional development)	Advisor
Controlling the health and protection of greenhouse vegetable crops	2 days	unknown	NO	SEMAE, France	https://formation.semae.fr/maitriser-etat-sanitaire-protection-cultures-potagere-serre#programme	Vocational training	

Efficient use of biocontrol tools	2 days	2024, November	NO	SEMAE, France (Céline Baudet)	https://formation.semae.fr/utiliser-efficacement-les-outils-du-biocontrole#programme	Vocational training	Technician, Crop Protection manager
From seed to seed: Farmers' vegetable seed production (De la graine à la graine : production de semences paysannes et jardinières)	one or two days		NO	RSP	https://www.semencespaysannes.org/images/vie_du_reseau/2023/R%C3%A9pertoire_Formation_.pdf	Vocational training	Vegetable growers, gardeners, community seed networks
Improve seed germination - level 2 (Améliorer la GERMINATION des semences - niveau 2)	one day	15/10/2023	NO	SEMAE	https://formation.semae.fr/biologie-et-qualite-des-semences	vocational	Laboratory technicians Crop technicians Managers of laboratories and production units
Maintaining and selecting farmers' vegetable seeds (Conserver et sélectionner les semences paysannes potagères)	two days		NO	RSP	https://www.semencespaysannes.org/images/vie_du_reseau/2023/R%C3%A9pertoire_Formation_.pdf	Vocational training	(future) vegetable growers interested in agroecology and seeds
Master 2 - Seeds and seedlings (Master 2 - Semences et Plants)		end : 2023	YES	Université Angers	https://formations.univ-angers.fr/plugins/odf-web/odf/_content/subprogram-parcours-semences-et-plants.pdf	academic	Future experts in seed production, quality and marketing
Master 2 - Seeds and seedlings (Master 2 - Semences et Plants)		starts 2024	YES	Nantes Université	https://sciences-techniques.univ-nantes.fr/formations/masters/master-biologie-vegetale	academic	Future experts in seed production, quality and marketing
Master Class Seed Technology	5 days	yearly,	NO	WUR	https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&cad=rja&ua	post-academic	professional seed technologists at MSc or PhD level, or those who

		next in oct 2023			ct=8&ved=2ahUKEwiP94S9-4r AhW4VKQEHfRKCaIQFnoECAoQAw&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.wur.nl%2Fen%2Fshow%2Fmasterclass-on-seed-technology-15-19-october-2023.htm&usg=AOvVaw3Z6zuGICqxt1ortwfy0oAa		have acquired an equivalent expertise through experience. Participants may be affiliated with industry, research institutes, seed quality laboratories, universities or other governmental institutions.
Mastering seed treatments (Maîtriser le poste traitement de semences)	two days		NO	SEMAE	https://formation.semae.fr/maitriser-le-poste-traitement-de-semences	vocational	Seed plant managers Seed processing unit managers Seed treatment managers and operators /!\ Not exclusively organic!
MSc in Horticulture: Seed Science and Technology	4 semesters (full-time)	2023	YES	Poznań University of Life Sciences	http://msc-bsc.puls.edu.pl/courses/#1520503561093-5830f2e5-3eb8	academic	Students
Optimising seed sorting (Optimiser le triage des semences)	two to three days		NO	SEMAE	https://formation.semae.fr/optimiser-le-triage-industriel-des-semences	Vocational training for industrial seed plants	Seed plant managers Seed sorting unit managers Seed sorting technicians and operators
Organic seed production	2 days	2024, June	NO	SEMAE	https://formation.semae.fr/la-production-semences-biologiques	Vocational training	Technician, Lab manager, Firm manager
Organic seed production - vegetable seeds special (under shelter)	2 days	unknown	NO	SEMAE, France	https://formation.semae.fr/maitriser-production-semences-potageres-sous-abris-ab#programme	Vocational training	Technician, Crop manager

Organic seed production in arable crops	two days	21/11/2023	NO	SEMAE, France	https://formation.semae.fr/la-production-semences-biologiques	Vocational training (adult and professional development)	Managers and technicians in seed production Plant managers Laboratory managers
OSA's Asynchronous Seed Production Course	self-paced, based on 1 intro + 6 modules	2023	NO	Organic Seed Alliance, USA	https://seedalliance.org/osas-asynchronous-seed-production-course/	Vocational training	seed students who are not working on a seed farm or being mentored
OSA's Organic Seed Production Online Course	6 months	2022, again in 2023	NO	Organic Seed Alliance, USA	https://seedalliance.org/2023/organic-seed-production-online-course-2/?emci=72a65e32-1bbd-ed11-a8e0-00224832e811&emdi=389d58d0-1cbd-ed11-a8e0-00224832e811&ceid=3012983	Vocational training	beginning producer working on a seed farm
Phytopathology basics	2 days	2024, October	NO	GEVES, Semae	https://formation.semae.fr/bases-de-phytopathologie#informations-pratiques	Vocational training	
Plant seeds: what's at stake for our future?	14 hours (7 weeks)	February to October 2024	NO	Institut Agro-Rennes-Angers	https://www.agreenium.fr/u/formation/391	Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)	Vast target group, including the general public
Practicing analysis on seed pathology (Pratique des	five days		NO	SEMAE	https://formation.semae.fr/pratique-des-analyses-de-pathologie-sur-	vocational	Any person who will conduct seed analysis

analyses de pathologie sur semences)					semences#objectifs-public-concerne-prerequis		
Practicing seed lot sampling in seed plants (Pratique de l'échantillonnage des lots à l'usine)	two days	22/1 1/20 23	NO	SEMAE	https://formation.semae.fr/pratique-de-l-echantillonnage-des-lots-a-l-usine#objectifs-public-concerne-prerequis	vocational	Staff in charge of seed sampling in seed plants
Practicing seed purity analyses and counts on seeds (Pratique des analyses de pureté et dénombrement sur semences)			NO	SEMAE	https://formation.semae.fr/pratique-des-analyses-purete-denombrement-semences	vocational	Any person who will conduct seed analysis
Production of vegetable seeds of farmers' cultivars (Produire des semences potagères issues de variétés paysannes)	10 days	March and April 2023	YES	CFPPA	https://www.cfppa-bourg-les-valence.fr/detail-formation/alias/produire-des-semences-potageres-issues-de-varietes-paysannes.html	Vocational training	(future) farmers planning to produce vegetable seeds
Saving vegetable seeds	1 day	22/1 1/20 21	NO	Bio Hauts-De-France	https://www.bio-hautsdefrance.org/formation/liste-des-formations/autoproduire-ses-semences-potageres/	Short vocational training	Farmers (organic and conventional)
Seed biology: Main principles, Level 1 (Biologie des semences : les grands principes - niveau 1)	1 day		NO	SEMAE	https://formation.semae.fr/biologie-des-semences-grands-principes	vocational	Staff integrating a seed production environment wanting to better understand their working environment
Seed collection and multiplication of herbaceous	5 days	2024 , may	NO	VEGEPOLYS	https://www.vegepolys-valley.eu/actualites/14209-formation-sur-la-collecte-de-graines-et-la-multiplication-	Vocational training	seed collectors, seed multipliers and future collectors and/or

seeds as part of the Végétal local brand		to june			de-semences-herbacees-dans-le-cadre-de-la-marque-vegetal-local-3-modules-de-mai-a-juin-2024.html		producers of herbaceous plant seeds, seedling producers
Seed multiplication Intensive course (Samenbau-Intensivkurs)	4 days	2024, March to September	NO	Pro Specie Rara	https://www.prospecierara.ch/de/erleben/veranstaltungen/veranstaltungen-detail/events/samenbau-intensivkurs.html	Vocational / amateur training	Experienced home gardeners, technical staff in the "green sector"
Beginners' course seed multiplication	3 hours	16.8. 2024	NO	Pro Specie Rara	https://www.prospecierara.ch/erleben/veranstaltungen/veranstaltungen-detail/events/samenbaukurs-fuer-einsteigerinnen-zuerich.html	amateur training	everyone (who wants to try multiplication of easy to multiply crops in a home garden or balcony)
Micro-farm training module XI "Seed and seedling production"	2 days	8-9 sept 2023	NO	u-farming	https://www.u-farming.ch/laformation	vocational	Anyone who has a project and the motivation to start a farming enterprise on a small piece of land (without prerequisite)

Annex 4: Library of learning resources - outcome of the benchmarking process

The library of learning resources was divided into several sub-groups, according to type of resource.

- (i) Text documents
- (ii) Commercial resources, mostly books
- (iii) Digital tools and references
- (iv) Showcases and teaching kits
- (v) Videos, webinars and presentations

Task 3.5 : benchmark : Text documents

Informations about those materials

Title	Source	Language	Year	Link	Type of resource	Access	Cost	Resource owner (Name of the autor, of the structure)
A seed saving guide	Organic Seed Alliance	EN, ES	2010	https://seedallian	Booklet	free		Micaela Colley, Organic Seed Alliance Dr. John Navazio, Organic Seed Alliance Lisa DiPietro, Organic Seed Alliance
Bean Seed Treatment: a simple approach without specific laboratory equipment (BRESOV Practice Abstract)	Organic Farm Knowledge platofrm	EN	2019	https://organic-fa	Sheet	free		0 Joelle Herforth-Rahmé
DOSSIER Cereal seed station: A demanding process Dossier with articles, infographics, videos. Infographics: Alveolar sorter, cleaner-separator, densimetric table, optical sorter, sorting & treating line	SEMAE	FR		https://www.semae	Infographics	Free		Semae, use authorised for teaching only?
Climatic Considerations for Seed Crops: Guidelines and Field Trainings for Organic and Specialty Vegetable Seed Producers	OSA	EN	2013	http://seedallianc	Book	free, online (upon giving email address)		OSA
Crop specific leaflets and videos on the seed production of many crops; including specific leaflets on organic seed production for: lentils, onions, squash (zucchini), carrot, coriander, cabbages, lettuce, bean, chickpea	FNAMS, ITAB	FR	2021	https://www.fnams	Leaflets and videos	free, online upon creating and account		FNAMS
General principles of organic seed production	FNAMS, ITAB	FR	2021	https://www.fnams	Leaflet (4pages)	free, online upon creating and account		FNAMS
CSB Manual #1 Establishment, management and governance	DYNAVERSITY	EN,FR,IT,ES,HU	2020	https://liberatediv	Text (Manuals series)	free		0 ECLLD Members
Deliverable 2.8: Proposal for a toolbox for identification and description of organic heterogeneous material	LIVESEED	EN	2020	https://www.livese	Document	free		0

Ekologiczna produkcja nasienna - Organic seed production	Centrum Doradztwa Rolniczego w Brwinowie	PL	2017	https://www.google.com/search?q=organic+seed+production&rlz=1C1GCE9Z_CentrumDoradztwaR...	booklet	free		0	Barbara Szońska, Centrum Doradztwa Rolniczego w Brwinowie Oddział w Radomiu
Infographic on Incentives for farmers to use organic seed	LIVESEED	EN, HU	2022?	https://www.liveseed.eu/	Infographic	free		0	
Magfogási Praktikum=Seed Handling Practicum	Magház	HU		https://maghaz.hu/	Brochure	free			Renáta Bócsó, Judit Fehér, Attila Juhász, Csilla Kiss, Dr. László Kiss, Orsolya Kiss-Kovács
Making your own germination tests (Faire ses tests de germination)	Agrobiopérigord	FR	2013	http://agrobioperigord.fr/	Leaflet	free			Agrobiopérigord
Managing Diseases of Tomato in the Midwest Using Organic Methods	eorganic	EN	2017	https://eorganic.org/	Leaflet	free			
Meadow plants: field checks	SEMAE	FR		https://www.semae.org/	Infographic	Free			Semae, use authorised for teaching only?
Meadow plants: seed multiplication (Plantes prairiales : multiplication de semences)	SEMAE	FR		https://www.semae.org/	Infographic	Free			Semae, use authorised for teaching only?
Meadow plants: sorting seeds of forage crops (Plantes prairiales : triage des semences fourragères)	SEMAE	FR		https://www.semae.org/	Infographic	free uploaded on project Sharepoint			Semae, use authorised for teaching only
Organic Heterogeneous Material	LLD	EN	2022	https://liberatediv.com/	Booklet	free		0	Seed4All
Organic cultivar trials and seed health	LIVESEED	EN	2020	https://www.liveseed.eu/	Infographic	free		0	
Organic seeds: what do the regulations say? (Semences biologiques : que dit la réglementation ?), article	SEMAE	FR		https://www.semae.org/	Article	free			Semae
Practical guide: Organic cereal seed production (Guide pratique - Produire des semences de céréales en agriculture biologique)	FNAMS	FR	2021	https://www.fnams.org/	Booklet	free (on line) / chargeable	0 - 15 euros		FNAMS
Practical guide: Seed drying (Guide pratique - Le séchage des semences)	FNAMS	FR	2020	https://www.fnams.org/	Booklet	free (on line) / chargeable	0-20€		FNAMS
Practical guide: Seed harvest (Guide pratique - La récolte des semences)	FNAMS	FR	2020	https://www.fnams.org/	Booklet	free (on line) / chargeable	0-20€		FNAMS
Principles and Practices of Organic Bean Seed Production in the Pacific Northwest	OSA	EN	2007	https://projects.sagepub.com/	Leaflet	Free			OSA
Principles and Practices of Organic Spinach Seed Production in the Pacific Northwest	OSA	EN	2007	https://projects.sagepub.com/	Leaflet	Free			
Proper seed storage	LIVESEED	EN	2020	https://www.liveseed.eu/	Leaflet	Free		0	Steven P.C. Groot (Wageningen University & Research); steven.groot@wur.nl; ÖMKI Hungarian Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
Recueil de savoir-faire paysans : produire des semences potagères bio	GABB Anjou	FR	2022	https://www.gabb.org/	Booklet	open access, online	0€ digital version		GABB Anjou
Seed Cleaning Toolkit	OSA	EN		https://seedalliance.org/resources/seed-cleaning-toolkit?emci=8f520568-9be8-ee11-aaf0					
Seed Quality: Best Practices for Vegetable Seed Handling in Montana	OSA	EN	2018	https://seedalliance.org/	Handbook	free			
Seed Science and Technology. Biology, Production, Quality	Springer	EN		https://link.springer.com/	Book	open access, online			Springer
Seed Storage - Don't Waste Your Efforts	Prophyta	EN	2017	Starting from page 32	Short article (3p)	Free			Steven G. Groot / WUR

Seed treatments allowed in organic farming in certain countries (Input list)	LIVESEED	EN	2020	https://orgprints.org/	Booklet	Free	0	Xenia Gatzert, Jochen Leopold, Rolf Mäder, Freya Schäfer (FiBL) ; contact: xenia.gatzert@fibl.org; ÖMKI Hungarian Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
Species-specific leaflets on seed saving for Apiaceae, Alliaceae, Cucurbitaceae, Asteraceae, Fabaceae, Solanaceae, Brassicas	Agrobiopérigord	FR		http://agrobioperigord.org/	Leaflet	free		Agrobiopérigord
Vetőmagkezelésre alkalmas anyagok és eljárások vizsgálata az ökológiai gazdálkodásban = Examination of materials and methods potential for organic seed treatment	Corvinus University of Budapest	HU, thesis book in EN	2010	Draft EN: http://phdissertation.org/	Ph.D. dissertation	free		Andrea Tóbiás
Organic Seed Resource Guide	eOrganic	EN	2009	https://eorganic.org/	Extension	free		Organic Seed Alliance, Oregon State University, Organic Materials Research Institute
Guidelines for testing the quality of farm-saved vegetable seed / Leitfaden zur Qualitätsprüfung von On-farm erzeugtem Saatgut von Gemüsearten	Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, VERN	DE	2014	https://www.agrar.de/	Extension	Free, online		Humboldt Universität zu Berlin
Pflanzenmikrobiome: verborgene Netzwerke für die Gesundheit	Rundgespräche Forum Ökologie, Bd. 47 »Die unbekannte Welt der Mikrobiome«, S. 71-78.	DE	2019	https://publikationen.tugraz.at/	Outreach	Free, online		TU Graz
Le microbiote des plantes, de son rôle dans la survie végétale à son ingénierie pour une agriculture durable	Planet Vie - Ressources en sciences de la vie pour les enseignants et enseignantes	FR	2022	https://planet-vie.enscm.fr/	Outreach / schooling	Free, online		Planet Vie - Ressources en sciences de la vie pour les enseignants et enseignantes
International rules of seed testing (evaluate seed quality)	ISTA	EN (also FR, DE; ES)		https://www.seedtest.org/en/publications/international-rules-of-seed-testing/	Document	Free (seed health), Membership	Some free (seed testing), some >200 CHF	International seed Testing Society
Leitfaden Saatgutgesundheit im Ökologischen Landbau - Ackerkulturen	FiBL shop	DE	2007	https://www.fibl.org/	Document	Free	0	
Leitfaden Saatgutgesundheit im Ökologischen Landbau - Gemüsekulturen	FiBL shop	DE	2007	https://www.fibl.org/	Document	Free	0	
Bresov Practice Abstracts 5 and 13 on germinatio testing (cauliflower and broccoli)	Bresov Project	EN		https://bresov.eu/results/practice-abstracts/		Free		
Semences de céréales : technologie du triage selon les caractéristiques du grain (Cereal seeds : sorting technologies according to seed characteristics)	Semae / GNIS	FR		https://www.semae.fr/upload		Free		

Task 3.5 : benchmark : Commercial resources (books)

Informations about those materials

Title	Source	Language	Year	Link	Type of resources	Access	Cost	Resource owner (Name of the autor, of the structure)
Internal technical instructions for organic vegetable seed production		DE, ??			Internal technical instructions	could be made available by BSAG		
Organic Seed Production and Saving, The Wisdom of Plant Heritage	Chelsea Green	EN	2011	https://www.chelseagreen.com/product/organic-seed-production-and-saving/	Book	Chargeable	15,95 \$	Bryan Connolly, Chelsea Green
Saving organic seeds (Produire ses graines Bio)	Editions Terre Vivante	FR	2021	https://www.terrevivante.org/boutique/livres/permaculture-jardin-les-seedsavers-de	Book	chargeable	25 euros	Christian Boué
Seed Savers Handbook (Handbuch Samengartnerei)	Arche Noah, Pro Specie Rara, ÖMKi	DE, EN, HU, FR	2004-2022	https://www.loewenzahn.at/produkt/2352/handbuch-samengartnerei/ https://www.biokutatas.hu/hu/webshop/item/1057/magtermesztok-kezikonve https://www.lerouergue.com/catalogue/samences-potageres https://www.andrea-heistingner.at/manual-seed-saving/	Book	chargeable	35-40 euro	Andrea Heistingner, Zsolia Hoch
Seed to seed, Seed Saving and Growing Techniques for Vegetable Gardeners, 2nd Edition	Chelsea Green	EN	2002	https://www.chelseagreen.com/product/seed-to-seed/	Book	Chargeable	24,95 \$	Suzanne Ashworth
The Organic Seed Grower, A Farmer's Guide to Vegetable Seed Production	Chelsea Green	EN	2021	https://www.chelseagreen.com/product/the-organic-seed-grower-paperback/	Book	Chargeable	39,95 \$	John Navazio, Chelsea Green

Task 3.5 : benchmark : Digital tools and references

Informations about the materials

Title	Source	Language	Year	Link	Type of resources	Access	Cost	Resource owner (Name of the autor, of the structure)
Diagnostic guide	INRAE	FR		https://ephytia.inra.fr/fr/C/	Digital application	Free		RMT Végédiag
E-phytia				https://ephytia.inra.fr/fr/H/	A portal of resources and applications for identifying diseases and pests, applying biological protection methods and carrying out epidemiological surveillance.	Free		
Main diagnostic and detection methods used by plant health organizations.	RFSV	FR		http://www.rfsv.fr/moodle/	Website	Free		RFSV
Moisture content calculator	Rhino Research drying beads website	EN		http://www.dryingbeads.org/	Calculation tool to calculate seed moisture content from temperature and RH	free		Rhino Research ?
Organic Seed Production Tutorials (Beets, Brassicas, Carrots, Lettuce, Onions, Swiss Chard, Wet-seeded crops)	OSA	EN		https://seedalliance.org/p/	self-directed online course	open account on website		OSA
Photo bank	SEMAE	FR		https://www.semae-pedag/	Pictures	Free		Semae, use authorised for teaching only?
Quick reference and how-to guides for organic seed production of a large number of crops	OSA	EN, partly ES		https://seedalliance.org/all/	Reference and how-to guides (leaflets)	free, upon informing email address		OSA
Seed Crop Record and Harvest and Handling Seed Record	OSA	EN		http://seedalliance.org/wp/	Record sheets	free, upon informing email address		OSA
Seed economics toolkit, including Labour tracking and production planning tools for seed growers, as well as a calculation tool for planning stock and foundation seed.	OSA	EN		https://seedalliance.org/p/	Calculation tools and webinar	free, upon informing email address		OSA
Seed Watch (vigisemences)	INRAE	FR		https://ephytia.inra.fr/fr/P/	Digital application	Free		
EPPO Standards on phytosanitary measures	EPPO	EN (usual name of species in several languages)		https://gd.eppo.int/standa	Documents; database	Free, online; other features require membership		

Task 3.5 : benchmark : showcases and teaching kits

Informations about the materials

Title	Source	Language	Year	Link	Type of resources	Access	Cost	Resource owner (Name of the autor, of the structure)
Seed station : an optimized industrial process at the service of farmers	SEMAE	FR	2020	https://www.semae-pedagogie.org/publication/station-semences-un-process-industriel-optimize-au-service-des-agriculteurs/	Pedagogical toolkit with seed samples from each sorting step (cereals)	Free		Semae, use authorised for teaching only?
Service intermediate crops : the agro-écological transition toolbox (réglette « Cultures intermédiaires de service : la boîte à outils de la transition agroécologique »)	SEMAE	FR		https://www.semae-pedagogie.org/publication/reglette-cultures-intermediaires-de-service/	Fiel tool	Free		Semae

Task 3.5 : benchmark : videos, webinars and presentations

Informations about the materials

Title	Source	Language	Year	Link	Type of resources	Access	Cost	Resource owner (Name of the autor, of the structure)
Seed saving of different species, including isolation, cleaning, storage	Longo Mai	EN, Fr, De, Es, Pt, Hu		https://www.diyseeds.com	Website with videos	free	0	
The densimetric table: A major impact on seed quality	SEMAE	FR		https://www.semae-pe.fr	Vidéo	Free		Semae, use authorised for teaching only?
The laboratory: For risk-free emergence	SEMAE	FR		https://www.semae-pe.fr	Vidéo	Free		Semae, use authorised for teaching only?
(1) Why heterogeneous material; (2) Experiences from the temporary experiment with heterogeneous material; (3) Upcoming temporary experiment on organic varieties suited for organic production	LIVESEED	EN	2018	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/51111	Slides (presentation)	free	0	Monika Messmer
Hot water seed treatment		EN	2023	https://www.seedambassadors.org	Slideshow	free		
Management Considerations for Seed Quality	Organic Seed Alliance, eOrganic and collaborators on a NIFA OREI	EN	2023	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3FGz7t1U8j0	Webinar	free		OSA
Organic Heterogeneous Material - Anders Borgen (Monimuotviljat webinaari - Heterogenous seed materials webinar* 14th November, 2022)	BOOST (Organic RDD-6) and DIVERSILIENCE (CoreOrganic)	EN	2022	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/51111	Video-webinar	free	0	Anders Borgen
Organic Heterogeneous Material, what is it and what are the potential benefits for the organic sector? By Matteo Pettiti	LIVESEED	EN	2020	https://www.liveseed.eu	Video, ppt	free	0	Matteo Pettiti
Organic Seed Production Six Webinar Series Part 6: Seed Contracting and Economics	Organic Seed Alliance	EN	2016	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3FGz7t1U8j0	Video	free		
Organic Seed Production Webinar #5: Cleaning and Record Keeping	OSA	EN		https://seedalliance.org	Webinar	free		OSA
Scaling up Seed Production	Organic Seed Alliance, eOrganic and collaborators on a NIFA OREI	EN	2023	https://youtu.be/3FGz7t1U8j0	Webinar	free		
Seed Economics Intensive Part 1: Inventory Management	Organic Seed Alliance	EN	2018	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3FGz7t1U8j0	Video	free		Tessa Peters
Self-Guided Tutorial in Organic Seed Production	OSA	EN	2016	https://seedalliance.org	Webinar series	Free, online		OSA
Vegetable Seed Production: Scaling Up: Steve Peters, Organic Seed Alliance	Organic Seed Alliance	EN		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3FGz7t1U8j0	Webinar			
Microbial Hitchhikers on Seed: Friend or Foe?	OSA	EN	2018	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3FGz7t1U8j0	video (webinar)	free	free	Organic Seed Alliance
Cereal seed station: A demanding process	SEMAE	FR		https://www.semae-pe.fr	Vidéo	Free		Semae, use authorised for teaching only?

Annex 5: Tools designed for task 3.5

- **Reflexivity grid on training trainers in organic seed production**

During the trainers' training session that took place at the start of the project, a checklist was drawn up for participants (experts on the subject in their countries). Based on the task reference framework developed for the post-harvest phase, the aim was to check that the reference framework was complete and relevant. Below is an extract from this checklist, which participants were asked to complete during the training session.

Competencies and sub-competencies		Comments:	
<p>1 >> Define an optimal strategy to harvest and thresh or extract seed: decide when to harvest (recognise seed maturity stages); decide what to do with the harvest (leave to dry/mature in the field; thresh or extract; store before threshing...)</p>	Decide when and how to harvest	Identify the maturity stage of a seed	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Is this sub-competency relevant? Do the contents of the trainers' training allow to cover it? 2. What do you think is missing? 3. What exercise (learning situation) might help acquire this sub-skill (distinguishing between beginners and trainees who already have experience with seed production and/or organic farming)
		Identify the maturity stage at the plant and field level	
		Identify and consider the other factors (weather conditions, availability of equipment and labour force) to decide on the optimal time for harvest	
		Decide when and how to harvest, taking into consideration a combination of factors	
		Be aware of the different harvesting methods available, the possible types of equipment and their (dis)advantages. The method depends on the crop species.	
	Implement the extraction or threshing method (if dissociated from plant harvest)	Threshing: Evaluate the moisture rate in the harvested material (by touch) - critical especially for large seeds which break at threshing if too dry.	
		Extraction: Implement the extraction process, identify the risks of extracting too early or too late (in fermentation process, in particular)	
		Fermentation: Identify the stage of the fermentation process to optimise seed extraction	

1

- **Training evaluation questionnaire for training designers**

Several partners were required to set up at least one pilot training course in their country for stakeholders in the sector (different target audiences depending on the training course) on seed quality and health management. These pilot training courses helped to develop the e-learning system for task 3.5 of the Liveseeding project. Once the pilot training courses had been completed, each partner was asked to complete a self-assessment questionnaire on the design and implementation of their pilot training course. The aim of the questionnaire was to identify the training engineering work carried out for the design and implementation of these pilot systems, and thus to support the partners in improving this training engineering work, particularly with a view to designing the e-learning modules.

Training designer survey

Introduction

As part of Liveseeding, you have committed to designing a training prototype ; or implementing an existing training course; to train professionals in pre- and post-harvest seed quality management. In order to conduct an analysis phase of these prototypes and their implementation, we ask you to please;

- answer the questionnaire below. Through questions on the preparation or implementation phase, we seek to identify how you did, and what could be improved.
- provide us with more information on the training program, by filling in the annex provided and copying into your file all the teaching resources you have designed and used.

1. Presentation of the training prototype designed (before implementation)

- Title of training prototype

Enter text here

- Targets targeted by the prototype (not actual targets)

What were the targets of your training ?

Activity	Job	Organic	Specialization
<input type="checkbox"/> Farmers' seed (networks)	<input type="checkbox"/> Producer	<input type="checkbox"/> have knowledges	<input type="checkbox"/> have to manage a
<input type="checkbox"/> Contract seed producers	<input type="checkbox"/> Advisor	<input type="checkbox"/> in organic	<input type="checkbox"/> large diversity of
<input type="checkbox"/> Handcraft small-scale	<input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input type="checkbox"/> production	<input type="checkbox"/> seeds
<input type="checkbox"/> seed enterprises	Enter text	<input type="checkbox"/> haven't any	<input type="checkbox"/> have to manage a
<input type="checkbox"/> Large scale /	here	<input type="checkbox"/> knowledge in	<input type="checkbox"/> small range of seeds
<input type="checkbox"/> multinational seed		<input type="checkbox"/> organic production	
<input type="checkbox"/> companies			

Level of expertise

- Beginner : want to start in seed production domain and haven't any knowledge about seed or grain production
- Insider : start in seed production domain, but have knowledges in grain production
- Intermediate: those who already have seed production knowledges
- Master: those who are expert in seed production

- Training prototype objective(s)

What was the objective of the training (formulate it in terms of "know-how" with an action verb, so that the purpose of the training device is clearly understood. The aim of providing knowledge is generally to solve a problem)?

Enter text here

- Planned duration of the training prototype

What was the total duration of the training system (including classroom hours, distance learning hours, e-learning hours and "work at home" or "training at work" hours)?

Enter text here

- Trainers for testing the first prototype

Who were the trainers and why were they the right people to train the trainees in the target skills?

Enter text here

- Place of training

Where did the training take place (specify face-to-face class: location, distance learning or e-learning class, on-the-job training)?

[Enter text here](#)

1.1 Preparation, implementation and evaluation of the tested training prototype

1.1.1 Training preparation: "How did you prepare the training?"

- Identification of training needs

Why did you decide to design and test this training prototype? How did you identify this training need? How did you define or choose the training objective(s)?

[Enter text here](#)

>> Did you miss anything when it came to identifying your target audience's needs? If you had to do it all over again, how would you go about it?

[Enter text here](#)

- Designing the training program and resources

How did you prepare the training? Who or what did you rely on to build the training program? How did you design the teaching resources: using existing resources, designing new ones, using what material?

[Enter text here](#)

>> Did you miss anything in preparing the training program and resources? If you had to do it all over again, how would you go about it?

[Enter text here](#)

- Choice of teaching methods

How did you go about choosing your teaching methods (face-to-face, distance learning, e-learning, group work, debates, presentations, etc.)?

[Enter text here](#)

>> Was there anything you missed or needed to define the appropriate teaching methods? If you had to do it all over again, how would you go about it?

[Enter text here](#)

- Choice of trainers

How did you go about choosing the trainers for your course?

[Enter text here](#)

>> Was there anything you missed or needed to define the appropriate teaching methods? If you had to do it all over again, how would you go about it?

[Enter text here](#)

- Choice of the place

How did you choose your training location(s) (classroom, field, laboratory, etc.)?

[Enter text here](#)

>> Was there anything missing or constraining you in defining the training location(s)? If you had to do it all over again, how would you go about it?

[Enter text here](#)

- Choice of evaluation system

Did you plan to evaluate trainee satisfaction? And did you plan to evaluate trainee learning? If so, please specify

[Enter text here](#)

>> Was there anything missing or constraining you in defining the way to assess trainee satisfaction and learning? If you had to do it all over again, how would you go about it?

[Enter text here](#)

- General

Generally speaking, do you have anything to add about what you missed in preparing the training, or what you would do differently?

[Enter text here](#)

1.1.2 Your assessment of the training prototype

- Participants and targets

How many trainees participated to the training course ?

[Enter text here](#)

Did the participants in your training course correspond to the targets you were aiming for?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes completely	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather no	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all
---	-------------------------------------	------------------------------------	-------------------------------------

- Achievement of training objectives

In your opinion, were the training objectives achieved?

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes completely	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Rather no	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all
---	-------------------------------------	------------------------------------	-------------------------------------

- Indicators

Can you tell us why you think the objectives were not achieved? On what do you base your assessment of these training objectives (a quiz at the end of the course, role-playing exercises, questions asked by trainees, oral and written feedback from trainees, etc.)?

[Enter text here](#)

- Additional informations

If you didn't answer "Yes completely" to the both first questions, please add further details

[Enter text here](#)

1.1.3 Ideas for improving the training prototype and its implementation

- Difficulties

Did you encounter any difficulties in implementing the training?

Enter text here

- Overall assessment of preparation and implementation

Finally, how would you assess the work you carried out to design and prepare the training system?

Enter text here

- Possible improvements

And if you had to do it all over again, what would you do differently? What areas of improvement would you identify for your training prototype?

Enter text here

Thanks a lot !

- **Tool to assist in designing learning situations for task 3.5**

In task 3.5, we aimed — not at producing a full educational scenario corresponding to the entire task reference framework developed, which would probably be too cumbersome to be usable — but tools for trainers (or training organizations) that would enable them to use the resources produced in Liveseeding to build an ad hoc training program based on the reference framework. To advance this work, at the annual meeting in September 2024, the Task 3.5 leaders led a workshop to design innovative and motivating teaching sequences based on the concept of “learning situations.” A grid was provided to help them design these situations, in addition to a plenary presentation of an overview of learning activities.

Workshop 3.5

Define a short or longer term strategy to sanitise a seed lot according to seed health issue(s) identified

List of participants	
----------------------	--

Here's the case study you'll be working on. **For 35 minutes**, in sub-groups, you will design **one or more learning activities** relevant to achieving the pedagogical objective of this case study.

Depending on the case, the learning activities we ask you to produce will have to be designed for a face-to-face classroom, a virtual classroom, or for self-study (at work, at home). This parameter is specified in the data provided for the case study.

The aim of this group work is to design learning sequences that are innovative and motivating for learners. **So try to think outside the box and be creative.** Enjoy your work!

1. Identity card and case study data

Below you'll find all the information you need to produce one or more learning activities: the training objective and the pedagogical modality chosen (face-to-face, virtual classroom, self-study), parameters that form the framework of your exercise, a list of learning activities and a list of pedagogical resources from which you can draw (but you're free to invent new ones) to design your learning activity.

TRAINING THEMATIC

Seed-transmitted plant diseases may appear during seed multiplication. They may be revealed in the field when symptoms appear in the crop, or after seed analysis. When this happens, the seed company, seed network or seed producer must define a strategy to sanitise this seed lot. This may include both short term and longer term approaches. Short term approaches include organic seed treatments (where appropriate) to reduce or eliminate seed contamination with the pathogen. Another short term approach may be to replace the seed batch with a healthy one from elsewhere. Longer term approaches may include adapting environments and practices of seed multiplication to avoid further disease spread or re-infection or selecting for more disease tolerance or disease resistance to the given pathogen in the concerned variety or population. Available and feasible approaches depend on which crop and which seed-transmitted disease is concerned.

TARGET AUDIENCE

Training is only effective if it is designed for a given audience, and related to the problematic work situations for that given audience. A training activity may therefore differ depending on whether it is aimed at an advisor from a small seed company or a network of seed producers.

Check the target audience(s) (preferably one type of audience, possibly 2)

- Farmers' seed (networks) Contract seed producers Handcraft small-scale seed enterprises Large scale / Multinational seed companies

Precise the target audience

--

Specify the target audience, its level of expertise (experts, beginners, intermediates) and whether the training concerns vegetable seeds or cereal seeds.

Check the "pre-requisite" level of the trainees

Beginner Intermediate Expert

Check the type of seeds concerned by the training

Vegetables seed Cereals

TRAINING STAKES AND OBJECTIVES

Describe here the training stakes for this audience (why it's important for them to acquire this skill) and the general training goal to achieve at the end of the training.

Training stakes and the general training goal for the target audience you have chosen

For the target audience we have chosen, acquiring the skill "Define a short or longer term strategy to sanitise a seed lot according to seed health issue(s) identified" is important because.....

At the end of the training, the trainee will be able to.....

MODALITIES

virtual classroom / face-to-face classroom / self-paced-training

MATERIAL AVAILABLE FOR BUILDING THE LEARNING ACTIVITY(IES)

- WP3.5 Skills framework
- EPPO database: <https://gd.eppo.int/>. Print-out of the EPPO datasheet on common bacterial blight of bean available, as an example: <https://gd.eppo.int/taxon/XANTPH/datasheet>
- Leitfaden Saatgutgesundheit im Ökologischen Landbau – Gemüsekulturen (Guidelines for seed health in organic agriculture – Vegetable crops) : <https://www.fibl.org/fileadmin/documents/shop/1481-saatgutgesundheit-gemuese.pdf> [print-out available]. For the moment only available in German.
- Leitfaden Saatgutgesundheit im Ökologischen Landbau – Ackerkulturen (Guidelines for seed health in organic agriculture – Arable crops) : <https://www.fibl.org/fileadmin/documents/shop/1480-saatgutgesundheit-ackerkulturen.pdf> [print-out available]. For the moment only available in German.

2. Description of the designed learning activity

TRAINING OBJECTIVES

Here are the training objectives

- Trainees can list 5 possible actions they can take to sanitize a seed lot.
- Trainees can list 5 elements they need to know about a given pathogen to establish an appropriate sanitation strategy
- Trainees are able to extract relevant information on a given seed-transmitted plant disease from different specialised sources (EPPO platform, national platforms on plant disease diagnostics, scientific papers) in view of establishing a strategy to sanitize a seed lot.
- Trainees are able to draft a sanitation strategy for 1 specific seed health issue and can break it down into an action plan.

Check one or several learning activities you have chosen to develop

Expositive methods – which emphasize the 'absorption' of new information. The learner need to listen, read, observe.	<input type="checkbox"/> Presentation : organized information on a specific topic <input type="checkbox"/> Demonstration of how a task can be performed <input type="checkbox"/> Worked examples with comment and explicit reference to the theory <input type="checkbox"/> Case studies real, significant cases related to the topic <input type="checkbox"/> other + with survey and feedback
Application methods – which emphasize the active processes that learners use to perform procedural and principle-based tasks and build new knowledge	<input type="checkbox"/> Demonstration and practice of a gesture or procedure <input type="checkbox"/> Analysis and diagnosis of a "virtual" case study (described in writing, audio or video recording) <input type="checkbox"/> Guided search for resources and production of a summary <input type="checkbox"/> Role-playing or simulation <input type="checkbox"/> Project: apply the principles and concepts learned in your own environment
Collaborative methods – which emphasize the social dimension of learning and engage learners in sharing knowledge and performing tasks in a collaborative way.	<input type="checkbox"/> Guided online discussions (chat, forum, video or audio conference): debate, exchanges <input type="checkbox"/> Collaborative work: application methods involving group collaboration (longer, more complex tasks) <input type="checkbox"/> Tutoring or even peer assessment: pairing up, for example, to assess each other's work/production.

THE DURATION OF THE PLANNED ACTIVITY, ITS VARIOUS STAGES AND TIMING

(e.g.: 1) sharing of instructions and distribution of materials - 5 min, 2) sub-group activity - 45 min 3) plenary sharing - 30 min 4) summary to be retained - 15 min 5) evaluation - 10 min 6) conclusion, follow-up and prospects - 15 min).

Describe duration, stages and timing of the activity

INSTRUCTIONS

Describe the instructions you're going to give trainees for carrying out the activity. Ideally, write down these instructions

MATERIALS

Describe the materials provided for trainees to carry out the activity (resources, Internet links, etc.) and specify how they will use the resources, and describe the link between the resources and the activity

PLANNED INTERACTION BETWEEN TRAINEES AND/OR WITH THE TRAINER

Describe it and specify in particular if it's remote (virtual class, self-training) the support used (chat tool, collaborative writing document, collaborative whiteboard, survey, etc.).

EVALUATION

Describe how you are going to assess what you have learned. Please note that the skills assessed must relate to the training objective you have formulated. If it's a quiz, true/false, MCQ, etc., write down the questions you might ask.

Annex 6: Programme of the trainers' training in Wageningen 4-5 April 2023 : Seed maturity, drying & storage

Tuesday, April 4th	
8h00	Meeting at the reception of Hotel Wageningsche Berg for departure
8h30	Meeting at the reception of the Forum building of Wageningen University, Introduction to the trainers' training (Stephanie Klaedtke), Participants' introduction, Introduction to the course (Steven Groot), (in room B0629)
9h35	<i>Coffee Break</i>
9h50	<u>Lecture 1</u> and group discussions: Seed development and maturation
10h40	<i>Coffee Break</i>
10h55	<u>Lecture 2</u> and group discussions: Seed Drying
11h45	<i>Sandwich lunch provided</i>
12h50	Assemble at Radix Building reception, Practical exercises 1: Drying systems, equilibrium RH and moisture content analysis
15h00	<i>Walk to room B0629; Coffee break</i>
15h20	<u>Lecture 3</u> and group discussions: Seed Storage
16h10	Visit of the gene bank (in 2 groups), Group discussions on applications
17h00	Practical exercises continued: Determine weight of drying samples
17h15	Departure to hotel
18h30	<i>Group dinner (optional)</i>
Wednesday, April 5th	
8h10	Departure from Hotel Wageningsche Berg
8h40	<i>Assemble at Radix building reception</i> , Practical exercises 2: Drying systems, Equilibrium RH, Moisture content experiment, (in room B0629)
10h00	<i>Walk to room B0629 and Coffee Break</i>
10h25	Demonstration of storage containers
10h50	Group and plenary discussions: Application of the theory in practice
11h50	<i>Sandwich lunch provided</i>
12h30	Assemble at Radix Building reception, Practical exercises 3: Drying systems, equilibrium RH and moisture content analysis
13h40	<i>Walk to Forum Building room B0629; Coffee break</i>
14h00	Experimental results reports and discussion; Personal action plans

